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Editorial

It is my sincere hope that, to the stalwart readership of *Early Music Performer*, the rebranding of the National Early Music Association's (NEMA) journal to *Early Music Performance & Research* will not come as too much of a shock to the system. It has been both a great pleasure, and a distinct learning curve, taking the reins from my predecessor, Andrew Wooley, who successfully guided the journal for thirteen years across 28 issues, and I hope my tenure will continue the successes achieved by those before me, and facilitate a smooth transition into the fast-changing world of academic journal publication.

As many readers will be aware, NEMA has now moved to a subscriberless model of funding, which has, amongst other things, necessitated a move away from print publication. Whilst some may view this as a detriment, I hope that this development in the life of the journal will prove to be a significant positive. The separation from the limitations of the print medium will manifest in myriad ways, not least through the immediate lack of physical page limits. Higher-resolution images of manuscripts can be provided in-journal, allowing for the reader to observe the historic materials on which we rely in greater detail than ever before. Additionally, a digital format allows us to integrate resources in a way that is simply not possible with print: links to online material can be provided and accessed with a click of the mouse; supplementary materials, such as tables of manuscript contents, full modern editions of pieces discussed, recordings of the music, can be provided either as separate downloads or at the end of the article/issue. As technology continues to plough forward, this new digital format allows us to follow closely behind, and embrace innovation as it arrives.

The current climate of music in the UK, academic or otherwise, is fraught. One needs only look to the several recent news items: from various opera companies having their funding either cut substantially or entirely; the BBC attempting (and, in light of significant public backlash, fortunately failing) to cut the BBC Singers; or that Oxford Brookes University plans to cut its entire music programme with almost immediate effect, ensuring the jobs of only a skeleton department to see out those students currently enrolled. The sector as a whole is in dire straits, and I feel that we have a collective responsibility to prove the overall worth

of the subject, be that in schools, universities, or in professional spheres. We must be more inclusive and innovative, and show that we are willing to adapt with the times, both in the small scale—by, for instance, working to achieve a greater gender parity in the editorial board of this journal—and in a grander sense across the board.

To further these ends, the move to a digital format allows us to make the journal completely open-access, with no fiscal barriers to authors or readers right from the point of publication. This will accompany an effort to gradually make the *EMP* back-catalog available too, and to create appropriate metadata to allow the journal to be searched and accessed via institutional and academic search engines – providing better access for all readers, as well as making the prospect of contributing to the journal a more appealing one.

Following this theme of renewal and looking to the future, we have decided to broaden the remit of the journal, to include a wider aspect of research into early music, not just focusing on performance. However, for anyone in doubt, or with reservations on this move, I want to assure you all that we are still striving to present excellent content pertaining to the performance of early music – with some exciting plans already in the works for future issues. I look forward to my tenure with great anticipation, and hope that we can continue to engage and satisfy our existing audience, as well as invite new readers into the community.

Samuel Teague

November 2023

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Il faut que l'air soit accommodé aux paroles Monsieur Lully gives a lesson in composition

John S. Powell

Molière's *comédie-ballet Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme* (1670) centers on Monsieur Jourdain, the son of a wealthy cloth merchant who seeks to rise above his bourgeois background by acquiring the trappings of nobility. Despite his age, and in the secret hope of marrying a marquise, Monsieur Jourdain has hired various tutors to instruct him in the gentlemanly arts of music, dance, fencing, and philosophy. In all his endeavors, however, the bourgeois manages to make a fool of himself by betraying his ignorance and bad taste—to the scorn of his pompous tutors and the delight of the audience.¹

The play begins with a scene of musical composition. A student of Monsieur Jourdain's *maître de musique* is shown alone on the stage setting the poem *Je languis, nuit et jour* to music. The student sings his air-in-progress in falsetto, shaping the vocal melody phrase by phrase and notating each phrase in turn.² Later in Act 1, Sc. 2, the *maître de musique* has a female singer³ perform the finished air for Monsieur Jourdain, which proves to be a serenade of ravishing beauty. But Monsieur Jourdain's musical tastes run in a very different direction, and he is unimpressed. 'This air seems a bit gloomy to me. It puts one to sleep, and I wish you could enliven it here and there' (*Cette chanson me semble un peu lugubre. Elle endort, et je voudrais que vous*

la puissiez un peu ragaillardier par-cy, par-là). The *maître de musique* replies with a truism: 'The air, monsieur, must be adapted to the words' (*Il faut, monsieur, que l'air soit accommodé aux paroles*).

This scene of musical composition is found in two manuscript copies of *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme*: a copy containing the entire play and its music (used for the examples below) made around 1690 by André Danican Philidor *l'ainé*, the keeper of Louis XIV's music library; and a commercial copy containing the music, made around 1706 in the studio of the music publisher Henri Foucault.⁴ When it appears in modern productions, this opening scene can be seen either as pure farce, with no other purpose than to elicit laughter from the audience,⁵ or as a practical lesson in composition couched in wit and humor.⁶ Adopting the latter interpretation, this essay will illustrate how the student thoughtfully shapes his music to fit the words by experimenting with and modifying various musical choices—thereby illuminating the creative process of a 17th-century French composer.

According to the printed stage directions, the pupil sits at a table and composes an air that Monsieur Jourdain has requested for a serenade (*un Élève du Maître de Musique compose sur une table un Air que le*

¹ For more context regarding the music of *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme*, refer to my chapter 'Le Bourgeois gentilhomme: Molière and music', in *The Cambridge Companion to Molière*, edited by David Bradby and Andrew Calder (Cambridge University Press, 2006), 121-138.

² This small role was performed by the versatile court singer Jean Gaye (ca.1640-1701), a *basse-contre* who could sing in the bass, tenor, and even soprano range (as seen here). Having performed in court ballets and *comédies-ballets* until 1671, Gaye joined Lully's Académie Royale de Musique in 1673 and performed major roles in *Cadmus et Hermione*, *Alceste*, *Thésée*, *Atys*, *Isis*, and *Bellerophon*.

³ This was played by the delectable singer Hilaire Dupuis (1625-1709), sister-in-law of the singer, composer, and singing teacher Michel Lambert...who was Lully's father-in-law. 'Mademoiselle Hilaire' sang in ballets at court beginning in 1657 and sang in the *comédies-ballets* of Molière and Lully until 1671; she did not join Lully's Académie Royale de Musique at its inception...probably because of her age.

⁴ I have used Philidor's MS as the basis of the musical examples as it is the most complete source. Both Philidor's and Foucault's MSS are available online with the International Music Score Library Project (IMSLP).

⁵ For example, the 2019 production by La Troupe du Théâtre de l'Echo du Robec severely shortens this opening scene and retains the finished <https://youtu.be/ljjh6PEj7Ac> (at 1 min. 55 sec. and 7 min. 20 sec. respectively).

⁶ The 1958 filmed production directed by Jean Mayer and Léone Mail included both the opening scene <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x4U9PQXHHE8> and the finished air (at 2 min. 5 sec. and 6 min. 42 sec. respectively), whereas the 2004 period production by Le Poeme Harmonique provided the most thoughtful and artistic rendition of both the opening scene and the finished air <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=h1HgO5pza24> and the finished air (at 2 min. 59 sec. and 5 min. 41 sec. respectively).

Bourgeois a demandé pour une Serenade). The *livret* does not mention the presence of continuo instruments on stage, so the presence of the bass line is ambiguous.⁷ Is it part of the act of composition, with melodic ideas that will eventually be used in the final version of the bass part, or does it simply serve as a neutral background to the student's creative process, unrelated to the air? Lecerf de la Viéville's account of how Lully composed an opera scene provides some perspective on the compositional process:⁸

que Lully agréoit une Scene. Lully la lifoit, jusqu'à la sçavoir presque par cœur : il s'établissoit à son Claveffin, chantoit & rechantoit les paroles, battoit son Claveffin, & faisoit une basse continue. Quand il avoit achevé son chant, il se l'imprimoit tellement dans la tête, qu'il ne s'y seroit pas mépris d'une Note. Lalouette ou Colasse venoient, auxquels il le dictoit. Le lendemain il ne s'en souvenoit plus gueres.

...Lully would read [the scene] until he knew it almost by heart: then he would sit down at his harpsichord, sing and repeat the words, play his harpsichord, and compose a basse continue. When he finished his melody, he would memorize it so well that he would not miss a single note. When Lalouette or Colasse came, he would dictate it to them. The next day he would hardly remember anything.

Lully composed the melody and bass line simultaneously while accompanying himself on the harpsichord, committed the music to memory, and then called on his assistants (Jean-François Lalouette and Pascal Colasse) to take dictation. In this opening scene we see the student composing only the vocal melody phrase by phrase, settling on his final version of each phrase and then notating it—he obviously didn't have the luxury of

assistants. Perhaps the bass line and implied harmonies are being imagined by the student at the same time they are audible to the audience, and in the creative whirlwind of composition the student does not take the time to notate them. In any case, some bass passages and melodic fragments that arise during the act of composition appear in the finished air.

Most likely the *maître de musique* gave his student the text of the serenade in advance...as he is not shown writing the poem. However, the student did not have to compose the air from scratch, for some musical decisions would have been dictated by the poetry. When setting French poetry to music, composers of the time followed the principles of French versification.⁹ Unlike the syllable-stress meter of English verse, French poetry was structured according to two principles: line length (the number of syllables) and end accentuation (the placement of the strongest syllables). Spoken plays of the period were usually written in rhymed alexandrines¹⁰ (lines of 12 syllables) with the primary accent at the end-rhyme and a secondary accent at the mid-point, the *césura*, which divides the alexandrine into two equal hemistiches of 6 syllables.¹¹ End rhymes were described as either 'masculine' (with the stress on the last syllable) or 'feminine' (with stress on the penultimate syllable), and the three main rhyme schemes of the period were *rimes plates* (aaBB), *rimes croisées* (aBaB), and *rimes embrassées* (aBBa).

⁷ The printed *livret* *Le Bourgeois-Gentilhomme, comédie-ballet donné par le Roy à toute sa cour dans le chasteau de Chambort, au mois d'octobre 1670* is available online on Gallica <ark:/12148/bpt6k83269v>.

⁸ Lecerf de la Viéville, *Comparaison de la musique italienne, et de la musique française. Cinquième Dialogue* (p. 215); available on Gallica, <ark:/12148/cb125043274>

⁹ For more on this subject, see Lois Rosow's excellent article, 'French Baroque Recitative as an expression of Tragic declamation', *Early Music* 11 (1983), 468-479.

¹⁰ The alexandrine was a medieval verse form used in the *chanson de geste* that was abandoned in the 14th century and was resurrected in the middle of the 16th century by the poets of the Pléiade (Jodelle, Baïf, Ronsard). The classical alexandrine became the predominant verse form in French tragedy.

¹¹ In the case of a 10-syllable line, the *césura* would fall usually on the 4th (or occasionally the 6th) syllable.

Je languis consists of a quatrain of alexandrines in *rimes croisées*—odd lines with feminine endings and even lines with masculine endings. Because the alexandrine divides into two hemistiches (often articulated with punctuation, as in lines 1 and 3), a composer would logically set them as pairs of antecedent and consequent phrases, as indicated below with red slurs:

Je languis nuit et jour, et mon mal est extrême
I languish night and day, and my pain is extreme

Depuis qu'à vos rigueurs vos beaux yeux m'ont soumis ;
Since your lovely eyes have subjected me to your harshness.

Si vous traitez ainsi, belle Iris, qui vous aime,
If you treat him so, lovely Iris, who loves you,

Hélas ! que pourrez-vous faire à vos ennemis ?
Alas! What will you do to your enemies?

One of the attractions of French poetry is the mute 'e' (*e muet*, or *e caduc*), which makes up almost a quarter of the vowel sounds. While generally dropped in spoken French, the mute 'e' is almost always pronounced in poetry—except when it is elided with the following vowel (as in *belle Iris*). The mute 'e' of a feminine rhyme is not counted in determining line length, so the first alexandrine contains 13 pronounced and 12 counted syllables, with the primary accent on 'extrême' (the rhyme) and the secondary accent on 'jour' (before the *césura*):

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 0
Je lan- guis nuit et jour, / et mon mal est ex- trê- me.

The third alexandrine of *Je languis* contains two examples of a mute 'e' ('belle' and 'aime'), the first one elided and the second one pronounced as part of the feminine rhyme:

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 0
Si vous trai- tez ain- si, / bel- le I- ris, qui vous ai- me.

Composers set the mute 'e' in different ways, depending on the context. When it elides with the following vowel (as in 'belle Iris'), both syllables are set to a single note. When the mute 'e' occurs at the end of a line, as in 'et mon mal est extrême',

it is usually set as a note equal to or shorter than the preceding stressed syllable—thus musically relieving the tension of the stressed syllable (underlined):

Je languis nuit et jour, et mon mal est extrême
Si vous traitez ainsi, belle Iris, qui vous aime,

The line structure of the alexandrine is set metrically so that secondary accent (the *césura*) and the primary accent (the rhyme) fall on the strongest beats of the bar. When a feminine rhyme coincides with a cadence (as in 'et mon mal est extrême'; see Ex. 1 from the finished air), both the accented syllable (red arrow) and the syllable ending in mute 'e' (blue arrow) could receive metrical accents by falling on successive strong beats:

Example 1

Finally, the student uses one of the most common song forms of the period: extended binary form. The A section contains the first alexandrine couplet and the B section the second alexandrine couplet. As the B section progresses, one or more lines are repeated with new music (hence the extended binary form). Typically, such an air follows a predictable tonal scheme: the A section would begin in the main key, modulate to a related key, and return to the main key toward the end of the B section. With the phrase structure, musical form, and harmonic scheme in place, the student composer then concentrates on 'adapting the music to the words'.

The A Section

The musical setting of the first two alexandrines occupies the A section. The student first composes a conventional descending half-step on 'languis' harmonized by a 4-3 harmonic suspension (Ex. 2, boxed in red) but immediately modifies it to the more inspired motif of a descending 4th (boxed in blue) accompanied by a chromatically ascending

bass (boxed in green). In the following bars, he writes down the melody and sings it to the syllables 'ou- ou- ou' for the last half of the phrase ('nuict et jour'):

L'Elève du Maître de Musique

Example 2

This opening melodic phrase frames the minor tetrachord (d-[c]-bb-a) and lingers on the ending Phrygian half step (bb-a).¹² The final version sung for Monsieur Jourdain in Act 1, sc. 2 reveals a further revision (Ex. 3): the bass line now traces an ascending tetrachord with the half-step at the top (d, e, f#, g, boxed in green), thereby mirroring the descending tetrachord in the voice (boxed in blue):

Example 3

In his music for the second hemistich ('et mon mal est extrême'; see Ex. 4), the vocal line begins a minor 6th higher (boxed in purple), and the anguished words 'et mon mal est extrême' are set in an upper, anguished vocal register. On 'extrême' the melody drops a diminished 4th (f-c#...boxed in blue), and for the next five bars the student notates the melody in doubled note-values. For the end-line rhyme the student first sets the mute 'e' to a half note a' on the weak beat of the bar (boxed in red),¹³ but five bars later he changes it to a descending *port de voix* (boxed in green):

Example 4

In the final version sung for Monsieur Jourdain in Act 1, sc. 2, the melancholy first hemistich ('Je languis nuit et jour') spans a melodic 4th (red slur), while the more passionate second hemistich ('et mon mal est extrême') expands the range to a 6th (blue slur). The *casura* (marked with a green arrow) occurs after the longest note on 'jour' and before the sudden leap of a 6th on 'et'. The bass underlying the first hemistich leads to a plagal cadence (red arrow) at the *casura*, and then continues to a half-cadence in A major at the rhyme (blue arrow):

Example 5

The first alexandrine describes the poet's suffering, the second reveals its cause as the severity of his beloved. Her cruelty and her bewitching eyes are described in two balanced phrases (Ex. 6), the *casura* articulated with a quarter rest (see green arrow). The student sings the first hemistich on 'la, la, ta, ta, la, la' (red slur), possibly notating the melody while singing, and then he sings the second

¹² This musical gesture in Baroque music has frequent associations with lament. For a more detailed discussion of this figure, see Ellen Rosand, 'The Descending Tetrachord: An Emblem of Lament' *The Musical Quarterly* Vol. 65, No. 3 (July, 1979), pp. 346-359.

¹³ In the final version the Foucault MS shows the slur between the eighth note bb and the half note a, which would give the mute 'e' a graceful agogic accent.

hemistisch with the text (blue slur), notating the music afterwards:

Example 6

The descending leap of a 4th and rising 2nd on ‘vos beaux yeux’ (Ex. 7a) recalls the opening motif of ‘Je languis’ from the first alexandrine (Ex. 7b):

Example 7a & 7b

Satisfied that he has composed a balanced period of antecedent-consequent phrases, the student stops his creative progress with an interrupted cadence (Ex. 8, boxed in red) and writes down the melody—eventually arriving at a full cadence in F major on ‘m'ont soumis’ (boxed in blue):

Example 8

As the *maître de musique* patiently explains to Monsieur Jourdain, ‘it is necessary, Monsieur, that the air be adapted to the words.’ The student has fashioned a binary air for the four alexandrine couplets by creating melodic shapes, motivic figures, and dissonant harmonies to match the syntax, inflection, and mood of the text. The internal structure of the alexandrine is reflected in balanced antecedent-consequent phrases, with cadences marking the secondary accent (the *casura*) and the primary accent (the end rhyme). Meaningful connections between words are made through association with the descending 4th

motif...first on ‘languis’ (the poet's suffering), then on ‘extrême’ (the degree of suffering), and finally on ‘vos beaux [yeux]’ (the cause of his suffering). The tension created by the melodic tritone ascent of ‘rigueurs’ (e'-b \flat , see red arrow, Ex. 9) is released by the melodic descent of a perfect 5th to ‘soumis’ (c''-f' see blue arrow). The bass mirrors this pattern of tension and release...tension through a melodic 7th descent to a low E during the first hemistich (green arrow), and release through a standard cadential pattern during the second hemistich (purple arrow):

Example 9

The B Section

The last two alexandrines are heard twice in succession, with melodic variants for the repeat. This couplet poses a question to the heartless maiden: ‘If you treat him so, lovely Iris, who loves you, / Alas! What will you do to your enemies?’ For the first hemistich the student composes a circular melodic line revolving around the notes a and b \flat (Ex. 10a). Apparently satisfied, he uses it verbatim in the final sung version (Ex. 10b), to which he adds a bass figure:

Example 10a

Example 10b

For the musically varied repetition, the student emphasizes the secondary accent of the

Monsieur Lully gives a lesson in composition

alexandrine ('ainsi') with an abrupt upward leap of a 5th to a dotted half note (Ex. 11a, bracketed in red)—and he retains this gesture in the final version (Ex. 11b), with a slight modification in the bass:

Example 11a

Example 11b

The second hemistich offers two mute 'e's. That of 'belle' clides with the first vowel of 'Iris' (i.e., 'belle_Iris'), and so the student correctly sets it as a single note. In his first attempt (Ex. 12a) he sets 'Iris' to a leap of a 4th on (see red bracket). This has two problems, as it closely follows the secondary accent on 'ainsi' and it places an untimely accent before the primary accent on 'aime'. He immediately modifies this 'Iris' outburst into a more composed repeated note gesture (blue bracket):

Example 12a

For the final version performed for Monsieur Jourdain, the student adds a descending melodic tritone g-c# in the bass (Ex. 12b; boxed in red), which also creates a dissonant harmonic tritone between the bass and the voice (boxed in blue) and casts the 'belle' of 'belle Iris' in an ironic light:

Example 12b

For the musically varied repetition (Ex. 12c), the student composes a contoured melodic phrase (red slur), which he then notates during the following measures (blue arrow) and articulates the last four notes vocally as he writes them down:

Example 12c

He uses this phrase, with a slight modification in the bass, in the final version (Ex. 12d):

Example 12d

The last alexandrine completes the poetic conceit ('Alas, what will you do to your enemies?'). The student experiments with different melodic gestures for the 'hélas' cry. First, he sets it as an outburst on the high e" (Ex. 13a, boxed in red) and then repeats it to the 'Je languis' motif (boxed in blue). For the musically varied repetition (Ex. 13b), he sets 'hélas' to descending minor 3^{rds} in an ascending sequence (boxed in green) over a chromatically ascending bass (bracket in red):

Example 13a

Example 13b

However, the last alexandrine presents some complications. The student makes the mistake of placing the unaccented first syllable of ‘pourriez’ on the downbeat of the bar and set to a long note (Ex. 14a; see red arrow)—thus wrongly accentuating the word. Then he confuses the word ‘fera’ (will do) with its homonym ‘faire à’ (do to):

Example 14a

To correct these errors, he shifts the unaccented first syllable of ‘pourriez’ to the upbeat (Ex. 14b; see red arrow), allows the strong syllable to fall on the downbeat (blue arrow), and changes ‘fera’ to ‘faire à’. However, he fails to elide the mute ‘e’ of ‘faire’ with the following ‘à’ (green arrow):

Example 14b

A comparison with the facsimile of this passage shows that while the text underlay of ‘faire’ is misaligned,¹⁴ the ‘à’ is clearly placed under the downbeat dotted quarter note a' (see green arrow):¹⁵

In the final version he adds a slur to specify that the two 16th notes of ‘-re’ are to be sung to a single

syllable (Ex. 14c; see red arrow).¹⁶ However, the elision of ‘-re’ with ‘à’ is left unaddressed:

Example 14c

For the musically varied repetition, the student experiments with different solutions. First, he tries an abrupt 5th descent from e'' to a' (Ex. 14d, see red bracket):

Example 14d

He then writes a more contoured melodic line that ascends a half-step to f'' followed by a scalar descent of a 10th to d' (Ex. 14e, see red bracket), with an elegant descending *port de voix* solution to the ‘-re_à’ elision (see blue bracket):

Example 14e

In the final version sung for Monsieur Jourdain, Philidor's MS shows that the first syllable of ‘faire’ falls on the dotted quarter note c# (see left facsimile, red arrow). The ‘-re_à’ elision is aligned directly below the eighth note b \flat (blue arrows) and ‘à’ is followed by what appears to be a syllable extension (green arrow)—with the b \flat slurred to the quarter note a on the downbeat of the next bar.

¹⁴ ‘fai’ should be placed under the dotted quarter note g#, and ‘-re’ under sixteenth notes f# and g#.

¹⁵ It is worth noting that Philidor's MS was an archival record of *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme* prepared by the king's music librarian (possibly from the original scores used at court) for the royal music library and was probably not intended for use by performers in actual performance. This may be the reason for the imprecise text underlay.

¹⁶ Corrections to the accidentals (enclosed in square brackets) are the inflections found in the Foucault MS.

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Foucault's manuscript (right facsimile) agrees with the text underlay of this 're_à' elision:

Philidor MS

Foucault MS

Here, the drooping melody of the poetic conceit 'que pourrez-vous faire à vos ennemis?' (Ex. 14f; bracketed in red) is anticipated in the bass line of the previous bar (blue bracket), beginning a jagged descent of a 9th before cadencing in D minor:

Example 14f

When the air is formally presented to Monsieur Jourdain in Act 1, Sc. 2, we can appreciate the delicious irony of the music master's understatement that it was composed by 'one of my pupils, who has an admirable talent for such things' (*un de mes écoliers, qui a pour ces sortes de choses un talent admirable*). Monsieur Jourdain protests that

the *maître de musique* should have composed it himself, and not delegated the task to one of his students (*Oui; mais il ne fallait pas faire faire cela par un écolier, et vous n'étiez pas trop bon vous-même pour cette besogne-là*). But the *maître* quickly assures him: 'You must not, Monsieur, let the name of student deceive you; these kinds of students know as much as the greatest masters, and the air is as beautiful as it can be' (*Il ne faut pas, Monsieur, que le nom d'écolier vous abuse. Ces sortes d'écoliers en savent autant que les plus grands maîtres, et l'air est aussi beau qu'il s'en puisse faire*). This begs the question: why did the *maître de musique* not compose the serenade himself? Did he consider the task beneath him and not worthy of a *grande artiste*, or perhaps did he not himself sufficiently possess the *talent admirable* to compose such a beautiful air? The status-seeking bourgeois was not the only target of Molière's satire. But the audience is in on the inside joke: that *Je languis, nuit et jour* was in fact composed by one of the 'plus grands maîtres' of 17th-century French music, Jean-Baptiste Lully.

John S. Powell

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October 2023

A complete transcription of Je languis nuit et jour is included on p.58.

What Handel Learned in Hamburg

The Composers of the Hamburg Opera and the Development of the Oboe as an Obligato Instrument, 1691–1705

Blake Johnson

The Oper am Gänsemarkt was one of the leading centers for opera in the German-speaking lands when an eighteen-year-old Handel arrived in Hamburg in 1703. The first public opera house in Germany, it was led at this time by the renowned composer Reinhard Keiser (1674–1739). The seventh in a line of distinguished composers to lead the opera in Hamburg, Keiser continued an operatic tradition with both French and Italian influences which Claude Palisca described as a ‘[...] melting pot of musical styles.’¹ The fifth of these composers, Johann Georg Conradi (d. 1699), has been credited with introducing the French operatic style to Hamburg.² Perhaps owing to Conradi’s French influence, the opera had spent more than a decade cultivating increasingly extensive uses of the oboe by the time of Handel’s arrival. The oboe was utilized in its first years for the operas of Jean Baptiste Lully (1632–87) to which Conradi was likely exposed during an earlier court appointment in Ansbach, which provides a possible explanation for the extensive use of the oboe in Hamburg which he began.³

As the oboe was still a fairly new instrument during the early 1690s, its extensive use in operas by Conradi and his successors constituted some of its first appearances as a solo instrument.⁴ With the oboe occupying a prominent role in both the Hamburg opera and Handel’s later works, it is

reasonable to infer that he was influenced by the music he performed and studied during his time there, which had introduced him to the oboe’s potential as a solo instrument. Composer Johann Mattheson (1681–1764), whom Handel quickly befriended upon arriving in Hamburg, suggested that Handel was strongly influenced by his time in the opera, writing that ‘[...] he knew little about melody till he came to the Hamburg operas [...]’⁵ Through an analysis of obligato oboe parts in operas by Conradi, Johann Sigismund Kusser (1660–1727), Keiser, and Handel, this article will track the early development of the oboe as an obligato accompaniment to the voice. My analysis will identify common characteristics of Conradi, Kusser, and Keiser’s approaches to writing for the oboe and analyze the influence of this style upon Handel’s own writing for the instrument.

Much scholarship has focused on instances of borrowing in Handel’s music; that is, his use and reworking of themes or motives from the works of other composers.⁶ Numerous examples of borrowing can be found in Handel’s music, including several from the works of Keiser, which he continued to reference throughout his career.⁷ Less attention has been given to Handel’s compositional approach in terms of the instruments he chose to utilize in his operas (and later his oratorios), how he approached writing for

¹ Claude V. Palisca, *Baroque Music*, 3rd ed. (Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 1991), 253.

² George Buelow, ‘Die schöne und getruer Ariadne (Hamburg 1691): A Lost Opera by J.G. Conradi Rediscovered’, *Acta Musicologica*, 44, no. 1 (1972), 108-21 (111); Bruce Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe: A History of the Hautboy From 1640–1760* (London: Oxford University Press, 2001), 138.

³ George Buelow, ‘Conradi, Johann Georg’, *Grove Music Online. Oxford Music Online*, <https://doi-org.proxy.library.umkc.edu/10.1093/gmo/9781561592630.article.06302>; Donald Burrows, *Handel* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994), 17.

⁴ Haynes noted that solo works for the oboe began appearing outside of France in the late 1680s and indicated ‘Care soglie a voi mi porto’ from Agostino Steffani’s (1654–1728) *Alarico* (1687) as the earliest aria with obligato oboe. This would have been closely followed by the arias discussed later in the article. See Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 122, 144; Agostino Steffani, *Alarico* (Leipzig: Breitkopf und Härtel, 1911), 18-19.

⁵ Johann Mattheson, *Grundlage einer Ebn-Pforte* (Hamburg, 1740), 73–4, translated in Donald Burrows, *Handel* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994), 17.

⁶ For studies of musical borrowing in Handel’s music, see John H. Roberts, ‘Why did Handel Borrow?’, *Handel Tercentenary Collection*, ed. Stanley Sadie and Anthony Hicks (Ann Arbor: UMI Research Press, 1987), 83-92; Ellen T. Harris, ‘Integrity and Improvisation in Handel’s Music’, *The Journal of Musicology* 8/3 (Summer 1990), 301-15; John T. Winemiller, ‘Recontextualizing Handel’s Borrowing’, *The Journal of Musicology* 15/4 (Aug 1997), 444-70; and David Hunter, *The Lives of George Frideric Handel* (Woodbridge, UK: Boydell and Brewer, 2015), 214-23.

⁷ David Hunter notes that Keiser’s works served as one of the principal sources for Handel’s borrowings. See Hunter, *The Lives of George Frideric Handel*, 215–21.

them, and what works or composers may have influenced these choices. Mark Stahura notes that while scholars have typically approached Handel's compositions in terms of either his use of voices or purely instrumental works, the orchestra was the '[...] working musical ensemble at the core of Handel's career [...]'⁸ The oboe in particular appears frequently in Handel's operas, regularly doubling the first violin line and receiving solo obbligato parts in more than ten operas.

1	Solo Oboe
2	Two Independent Oboe Parts
3	Two Oboes in Unison
4	Unison Oboes and Violins

Table 1 - Categories of Obligato Oboe Parts in Handel's Operas

With exception for accommodations made for the diverging abilities of his soloists, Handel utilized a common approach to the oboe across his operas (table 1), generally relying on four types of oboe accompaniment for his arias: solo oboe (Category 1), two independent oboe parts (Category 2), two oboes in unison (Category 3), and unison oboes and violins (Category 4). Oboist Sara Funkhouser identified common characteristics of each of these categories, with the solo oboe being used in slow, minor passages as a lyrical instrument to convey emotions such as grief or serenity; two oboes being used to convey a more cheerful character in faster tempos and major keys, often in 3/8; unison oboes following the same characteristics of the two oboe parts, but often in duple metre; and unison oboe and violin passages treating the oboe as a ripieno instrument which occasionally emerges for brief solos.⁹ These four categories and early traces of their respective characteristics can be found in Handel's first Hamburg opera, *Almira* (1705), in which Bruce Haynes noted that Handel included more obligatos for the oboe than in any other single opera.¹⁰

1	Concerted Aria
a)	Vocal Melody
b)	Contrasting Melody
2	Prelude-Ritornel

Table 2 - Subcategories of Obligato Oboe Parts in Handel's Operas

In addition to the aforementioned categories which deal primarily with instrumentation, I will make use of two subcategories to denote the way in which the oboe interacts with the voice: the concerted aria (subcategory 1) and the prelude-ritornel (subcategory 2), to borrow terms from Paul Henry Lang (table 2).¹¹ The concerted aria refers to an aria in which the oboe interacts directly with the voice, often including imitation between the two parts in thirds. This obbligato type can use either some form of the vocal melody (1a) or a contrasting melody (1b). The prelude-ritornel features the oboe as the leading voice of the ripieno, opening (and often closing) the aria and providing contrast between vocal phrases. This type is most often based on the vocal melody, but can vary. In these arias, the oboe and voice mostly trade off lines rather than interacting directly. In studying the use of the oboe in operas by the four composers listed above, I will focus on arias in which the composer specifically indicates the instrument, tracking the appearance of the categories I have outlined and analyzing stylistic connections in the oboe writing across the operas of these four composers.

Early Obligatos by Conradi & Kusser, 1691-95

In 1972, George Buelow wrote that little was known about Conradi outside of the dates of his birth, death, and court appointments.¹² Fifty years have passed and he is still a largely unknown composer, essentially known today only for his opera *Die schöne und getruer Ariadne* (1691), which since Buelow's article has received its first and only recording.¹³

⁸ Mark W. Stahura, 'Handel and the Orchestra', *The Cambridge Companion to Handel*, ed. Donald Burrows (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997), 238-48 (238).

⁹ Funkhouser, 'An Evaluation of G. F. Handel's Use of the Oboe in His Arias', (MM thesis, University of Missouri-Kansas City, 1976), 14-16.

¹⁰ Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 315.

¹¹ Paul Henry Lang, *George Frideric Handel* (New York: W.W. Norton and Company, 1966), 617-20; Oboist Stephen Hiramoto has also made the connection between Lang's aria types and Handel's writing for the oboe, using the two types as two of three primary categories for solo obligatos in his analysis. See Stephen Hiramoto, 'Soloistic Writing for the Oboe in the Arias of Handel's Operas', (DMA diss., University of North Texas, 1996), 14-15.

¹² Buelow, 'Die schöne und getruer Ariadne', 110.

¹³ Johann Georg Conradi, *Die schöne und getruer Ariadne*, The Boston Early Music Festival Orchestra and Chorus, conducted by Paul O'Dette and Stephen Stubbs, recorded July 4 - 8, 2004, CPO 777073-2, 2005, CD.

Born in the town of Oettingen to organist Caspar Conrad, Conradi likely received his early training from his father.¹⁴ The year of his birth is unknown, but in 1671 he began the first in a series of appointments as a Capellmeister, beginning with Öttingen-Öttingen, where he remained for twelve years before moving on to Ansbach in 1683, during which time Buelow suspected Conradi was introduced to the French operatic style which would later come to dominate his writing.¹⁵ Conradi's introduction of this style to Hamburg is significant as it cemented a major component of the distinct combination of French, German, and Italian styles which would define the style of opera in Hamburg as it was further developed by his successors.

Conradi took over the opera in 1690 and while the lack of thorough records from the time precludes a definite knowledge of the makeup of his orchestra, the score for *Ariadne* shows that double reeds were a core part of the wind section. As Buelow noted, while the orchestra plays a prominent role throughout the opera, the exact instrumentation is not indicated for the majority of the work.¹⁶ This suggests that Conradi (likely through his copyist) simply specified exact instrumentation on individual parts or that he was unsure which musicians would be available for the performances. However, he did occasionally specify a particular instrument, often from the double reed family, including obbligato parts for both oboe and bassoon. Given that Conradi chose the oboe for one of the few indicated solo parts, it is likely that the oboes would also have doubled the violin lines for many of the arias. This is especially likely considering his French influence and probable familiarity with the works of Lully, in which the oboe's function is often that of a wind counterpart to the violin.¹⁷

Appearing in scene twelve of act two, 'Genigte liebe beglücke die Lust' is a duet between Phaedra of Crete and her husband Theseus (table 3).¹⁸ As table 1 shows, 'Genigte liebe' is written in triple metre and a major key, with two independent oboe parts. The cosmopolitan style of the Hamburg opera is already evident in this aria, with its German text and distinctly French style. While the two vocalists begin the aria on their own rather than after an introductory ritornello, the obbligato parts are firmly in the prelude-ritornel style. Like the two voices which enter in imitation, the two oboes imitate one another as they echo the rhythms of the voices between lines of text (ex. 1). The oboe parts are largely an instrumental repetition of the vocal lines until the very end, when they take over the melody for the final time. Here the oboes present nearly continuous quavers which lead to an ascending flourish which immediately cadences to close out the aria. 'Genigte liebe' is a brief aria and does not utilize the oboes outside of echoing the vocal melody, but coming from Hamburg's earliest extant opera, it points to the presence of capable oboists in the city and sets the stage for the more extensive uses of the instrument which were to come from Conradi's successors.¹⁹ This aria provides evidence of many of the stylistic features found in later arias, but moving forward, my analysis (outside of the tables) will be confined to arias with a single oboe.

Conradi's departure from Hamburg in 1693 left an opening at the opera which would be filled by another composer influenced by Lully and the French style. Born in Pressburg, Hungary, Kusser's career took him across the German-speaking lands, France, England, and Ireland. Never in one place for very long, Johann Gottfried Walther wrote that Kusser's frequent relocations were due to his '...volatile and hot-headed temperament.'²⁰

¹⁴ Buelow, 'Conradi, Johann Georg.'

¹⁵ Buelow, 'Conradi, Johann Georg.' Haynes noted that Lully's use of the oboe was adopted by other composers throughout Europe as late as the middle of the eighteenth century in both orchestral music and opera. See Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 279-80.

¹⁶ Buelow, 'Die schöne und getruene Ariadne', 116.

¹⁷ Lully also wrote for two or more oboe parts in his operas, either with voice or in purely instrumental sections which show similarities to Conradi's use of the instrument in *Ariadne*, as in the 'Prote'e et sa Suite' and 'Heureux qui peut voir du Rivage' from act I, scene V of *Phaeton* (1683). Jean Baptiste Lully, *Phaeton* (Paris: Christophe Ballard, 1683), 26-32.

¹⁸ Johann Georg Conradi, *Die schöne und getruene Ariadne* (Hamburg, 1691), M1500.C696 S44, Music 3271, Music Division, Library of Congress, Washington, DC.

¹⁹ Buelow, 'Die schöne und getruene Ariadne', 111.

²⁰ Johann Gottfried Walther, *Musicalisches Lexicon* (Leipzig: Wolfgang Deer, 1732), 189, translated in Samantha Owens, 'The Stuttgart "Adonis": A Recently Rediscovered Opera by Johann Sigismund Cousser?', *The Musical Times*, 147, no. 1896 (Autumn 2006), 67-80 (68).

What Handel learned in Hamburg

Aria Title	Category	Subcategory	Parts	Voice Type	Tempo	Metre	Key
'Genigte liebe beglücke die Lust'	2	2	2 oboe lines and continuo	Soprano and Tenor	N/A	3/4	C Major

Table 3 - Characteristics of Conradi's Aria with Obligato Oboes in Ariadne (1691)

69

Hautbois 1

Hautbois 2

Ariadne

Theseus

Bass

H 1

H 2

A

T

B

Example 1 - Johann Georg Conradi. *Die schöne und getruwe Ariadne*, 'Genigte liebe beglücke die Lust' (Act II, Scene 12, bars 69–78).

At some point before 1680, Kusser appears to have traveled to France. According to Walther, Kusser spent much of his time in France under the tutelage

of Lully, from whom he would have learned the French style which pervaded his later compositions.²¹ By 1680, Kusser had returned

²¹ Walther, *Lexicon*, 189-90, translated in Owens, "The Stuttgart "Adonis"", 68.

from France and taken up posts in Baden-Baden and Stuttgart, where his father, composer Johann Kusser, had been employed in 1674. Kusser continued to move around in the following years but in 1689 began composing for the opera house in Brunswick, where he would premier five operas before moving to Hamburg in 1694.²² With his knowledge of German and training in the French style, Kusser was an ideal successor to Conradi and continued the cosmopolitan style which was becoming Hamburg's norm.

As early as 1688, an aria with obbligato oboe had appeared in Hamburg in the opera *Xerxes* by Johann Philipp Förtsch (1652–1732).²³ As Förtsch's *Xerxes* is now lost, it is impossible to know how the oboe was utilized in Hamburg before Conradi's *Ariadne* and if its use extended beyond the call and response function employed in 'Genigte liebe.' However, when Kusser came to Hamburg, he began to write arias in which a single oboe engaged with the vocal part through both contrasting melodies and imitation. Haynes compared the function of the oboe in these arias to the treble voices of a trio sonata, similar to Lang's description of the concerted aria as being influenced by the concerto grosso.²⁴ Such an aria is found in Kusser's *Erindo* (1695), in one of the opera's few solo obbligatos (table 4).²⁵ 'Ach daß doch meine Pein' opens with voice and oboe engaging in imitation, with the vocal line restated in the oboe a third above the voice (ex. 2). After several bars of this, Kusser introduces contrasting rhythms in the two parts as Eurilla begins to elaborate on her troubles in the fourth line of text.

Ach daß doch meine Pein
Nur durch den Tod allein
Beendigt möchte seyn.
Weil mein betrübtes Herz
Nun fühlt der Liebe Schmerz
Zum Überfluß/
Da ich jetzt Scheide/
Und meine Freude
Mit höchsten Leide
Nun meiden muß.²⁶

Oh that my torment
by death alone
could be ended.
Because my saddened heart
now feels love's pain
in abundance,
since I am parting,
and my joy
with great suffering
must now shun.

As the voice reaches the word *betrübtes* (saddened), the oboe abandons the vocal line for a more rhythmically active motive which initially prolongs the G of the previous measure against the A in the bass (bar 8). Kusser opted not to utilize a minor key or frequent dissonances to bring to life the pain and resignation of Bressand's text. Instead, the oboe serves here as an extension of the vocal line, often presenting the same melody but occasionally pulling away to heighten the affect through more active rhythms and suspensions like that found in bar 8. Kusser utilized the same approach later in the aria, as the soprano reaches the words *liebe Schmerz Zum Überfluß* (love's pain in abundance). Here the oboe essentially ornaments the vocal line as it is happening, rising a fifth above the voice's final note for the bar and filling in the pitches in between as it leads into the next bar (ex. 3). The voice then takes this motive up in rhythmic unison with the oboe as they lead into the cadence which ends the oboe line. This close association of oboe and voice, with the oboe serving to heighten and elaborate upon the affect of the vocal line, was later developed further in arias by Keiser and Handel.

Example 2 - Johann Sigismund Kusser. *Erindo*, 'Ach daß doch meine Pein' (Act I, bars 20–2).

²² Owens, 'The Stuttgart "Adonis"', 68.

²³ Andrew D. McCredie, 'Instrumentarium and Instrumentation in the North German Baroque Opera', (PhD dissertation, University of Hamburg, 1964), 84.

²⁴ Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 138; Lang, *Handel*, 617.

²⁵ Johann Sigismund Kusser, *Erindo* (Hamburg: Niclas Spiering, 1695).

²⁶ Friedrich Christian Bressand, *Erindo: or the Blameless Love* (Hamburg, 1694), MS 640/3: 3, State and University Library, Hamburg.

What Handel learned in Hamburg

Aria Title	Category	Subcategory	Parts	Voice Type	Tempo	Metre	Key
'Ach daß doch meine Pein'	1	1a	1 oboe line and continuo	Soprano	Adagio	3/2	C Major
'Mich heist ihr gehorsam Beginnen'	2	1b	2 oboe lines and continuo	Tenor	N/A	3/4	C Major
'Was Wunders muß doch ein Verliebter machen?'	2	1b	2 oboe lines and continuo	Tenor	N/A	2/2	E Minor

Table 4 - Characteristics of Kusser's Arias with Obligato Oboe(s) in *Erindo* (1695)

Adagio

The musical score is presented in three systems, each with three staves. The first system is for Eurilla (Soprano), Hautbois (Oboe), and Bass. The second system is for E (Soprano), H (Oboe), and B (Bass). The third system is for E (Soprano), H (Oboe), and B (Bass). The lyrics are: 'Ach daß doch meine Pein Nur durch den Tod allein Be - en - digt möch - te seyn Weil mein be - trüb - tes Herz Nun fühlt der Lie - be Schmerz Zum Ü - ber - fluß'.

Example 3 - Johann Sigismund Kusser. *Erindo*, 'Ach daß doch meine Pein' (Act I, bars 1–12).

Obbligatos by Keiser, 1704

In contrast to the brief stints of his predecessors, Keiser became a long-time fixture of the opera in Hamburg. His first opera to be performed in the city, *Basilus*, was premiered in 1694, while Keiser was still employed full-time in Brunswick, with another premiered in 1696. Finally, Keiser relocated to Hamburg in 1697, where he would, with the exception of 1708, contribute at least one opera per year to the Oper am Gänsemarkt until 1717.²⁷ Keiser was highly acclaimed in his time, with Mattheson describing him as both the ‘premier homme du monde’ (first man in the world) and ‘the greatest opera composer of the world.’²⁸ His reputation outlived both himself and Handel, with English writers Charles Burney and John Hawkins praising his skill in their histories of music published in 1776. Burney wrote that ‘[...] for modulation, ingenuity, and new ideas, he had scarcely his equal.’²⁹ Burney’s comment seems to speak to the skill for tuneful melodies for which Keiser is best known and which surely encouraged Handel to borrow so frequently from his works. Hawkins spoke with a similar level of praise, writing that ‘[...] such was the native ease and elegance of his style, and such his command over the passions of his hearers, that all became susceptible of their effects.’³⁰

If Kusser’s use of instrumental obbligatos was moving toward an inclusion of the instrumental soloist in the portrayal of an aria’s affect, Keiser’s writing realized this practice fully, employing the oboe as an equal partner to the voice. Hans Joachim Marx wrote that it was in Hamburg that

Handel learned to use instruments to portray specific affectations and noted that ‘[...] Keiser’s scores enabled him to study the way an opera composer employed instrumentation to depict dramatic conflicts.’³¹ Christopher Hogwood also noted Keiser’s extensive use of instrumental color, suggesting that the German-speaking lands had a particular wealth of skilled instrumentalists.³² Hamburg itself likely possessed an advantage over many other German cities due to its ideal geographic location, strong trading economy, and rise as a global marketplace and financial center throughout the seventeenth century.³³ This solid economic standing would have enabled the public opera house to afford the best performers available, as evidenced by the extensive use of the orchestra in Hamburg operas.

Keiser made particularly extensive use of the oboe in his operas, both as a solo instrument and in unison passages with the violins. Mattheson noted that ‘In his treatment of instruments, especially the *Hautbois*, he was quite pleasing [...]’³⁴ In his *Nebucadnezar* (1704), Keiser utilized the oboe as a solo instrument in four arias (table 5).³⁵ Premiered during Handel’s time in the opera orchestra, Handel would likely have been in the orchestra for the run of the opera and Ellen T. Harris suggests that *Nebucadnezar* was likely among the scores of Keiser’s which Handel owned.³⁶ The arias with oboe in this opera show both connections to the style of Conradi and Kusser and also increasingly nuanced uses of the instrument as an equal partner to the voice.

²⁷ George Buelow, ‘Hamburg and Lübeck’, *The Late Baroque Era: From the 1680s to 1740*, ed. George Buelow (London: The Macmillan Press Limited, 1993), 191-215 (196).

²⁸ Mattheson, *Das neu-eröffnete orchestra* (Hamburg, 1713), 217; Mattheson, *Grundlage*, 133, translated in Buelow, ‘Hamburg and Lübeck’, 196.

²⁹ Charles Burney, *A General History of Music: From the Earliest Ages to the Present Period* (New York: Dover Publications, 1957), II: 462.

³⁰ John Hawkins, *A General History of the Science and Practice of Music* (London: J. Alfred Novello, 1853), II: 851.

³¹ Hans Joachim Marx, ‘The Instrumentation of Handel’s Early Italian Work’, *Early Music*, 16, no. 4 (Nov 1988), 496-505 (497, 500).

³² Christopher Hogwood, *Handel* (New York: Thames and Hudson, 1984), 26.

³³ For more background on the rise of Hamburg’s economy over the course of the seventeenth century, see Erik Lindberg, ‘The Rise of Hamburg as a Global Marketplace in the Seventeenth Century: A Comparative Political Economy Perspective’, *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 50/3 (July 2008), 641–62.

³⁴ Mattheson, *Grundlage*, 129, translated in Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 315.

³⁵ Reinhard Keiser and Christian Friedrich Hunold, *Salomon/Nebucadnezar* (Beeskow, Germany: Ortus Musikverlag, 2015), 73–207.

³⁶ Ellen T. Harris, *George Frideric Handel* (New York: W. W. Norton, 2014), 242.

What Handel learned in Hamburg

Aria Title	Category	Subcategory	Parts	Voice Type	Tempo	Metre	Key
'Müssen deine schönen Augen'	1	1a	1 Oboe line and Continuo	Soprano	N/A	4/4	D Minor
'Kein Mensch siegt über Seine Seele'	1	1a	1 Oboe Line and Continuo	Soprano	N/A	4/4	F Major
'Weine, blut!'	1	1a	Solo Oboe and Solo Violin	Soprano	Affettuoso	3/4	C Minor
'Du bleibst mein Leben'	2	2	2 Oboe Lines and Continuo	Soprano and Soprano	N/A	4/4	F Major
'Liebes krankheit'	1	1a	1 oboe line and continuo	Soprano	N/A	4/4	D Minor

Table 5 - Characteristics of Keiser's Arias with Obbligato Oboe(s) in *Nebucadnezar* (1704)

In 'Kein Mensch siegt über Seine Seele', the oboe and voice interact directly only once, with them communicating instead through the trading off of lines following the oboe's introduction of the vocal melody (ex. 4). The writing is more virtuosic and further independent of the vocal line, but the essence of Kusser's use of the solo oboe is still present. The text conveys Cyrene's fierce refusal of Belshazzar's pleas for her love, ending with Cyrene's conclusion that if Belshazzar wishes to have her heart, he '[...] must tear it out from my breast.³⁷ The oboe begins and ends the aria after the da capo, and presents a heightened version of the spirit of the text, rather than engaging in instances of specific text painting. As in the writing seen in bars 5 and 6, the vocal line is largely stepwise throughout the aria. The oboe is given more frequent and larger leaps and utilizes a much wider range. The virtuosic flourish in bar 2, spanning more than an octave, serves to set the defiant tone for the rest of the aria.

The text of 'Liebes krankheit' contrasts with that of 'Kein Mensch', describing Darius's heartbreak at being forced apart from Cyrene:

*Liebes krankheit hat gefahr
 Sie lässt eben
 Sich nicht heben
 Wie man meint;
 Liebes kinde
 Ritzt geschwinde/
 Und es scheint
 Daß zu weilen
 Sich zu heilen
 Müsse mehr seyn/ 16l sein Jahr.*

Lovesickness is dangerous,
 It does not
 Simply go away
 When one wishes it to;
 Venus' child
 Scratches you in an instant,
 But it seems
 That to wait
 To heal
 Takes longer than a year.³⁸

The oboe begins the aria alone, setting up the vocal melody which is characterized by its repeated quaver and two semiquaver figure (ex. 5). As the voice enters, it seems that Keiser is writing in the prelude-ritornel style, with the oboe and voice initially remaining separate until the end of bar 5. In the first half of the aria, the oboe interacts with the voice only to highlight suggestive words such as *Gefahr* (dangerous) in bar 5 and *weilen* (wait) and *heilen* (heal) in bar 10.

As Darius reaches his conclusion that 'to heal takes longer than a year', Keiser uses the oboe to aid in delaying the resolution as he repeats the final line of text five times in total beginning in bar 11 (ex. 6). The first statement of *Jahr* lands not on the leading tone, but a lowered seventh scale degree which functions as the fifth of a III chord, over which the oboe explores a repeated figure around the third of the chord (bars 12–13). The next statement of *Jahr* lands on an unaccompanied tonic which the oboe and continuo then recast as a IV chord (mm. 13–14). Over the voice's sustained D, the oboe moves around the root and third of the chord in a figure which grows in intensity through increasingly short note values. Haynes noted that in *Almira* (1705), Handel developed the soprano-

³⁷ Reinhard Keiser and Christian Friedrich Hunold, *Salomon/Nebucadnezar*, 52.

³⁸ Reinhard Keiser and Christian Friedrich Hunold, *Salomon/Nebucadnezar*, 60.

oboe dialogue into a more elaborate form by utilizing figures idiomatic to the oboe rather than the voice; Keiser's writing in this section anticipates that development one year earlier.³⁹ After a brief repetition on a V chord, the vocalist repeats the final three lines of text once more. The oboe joins just before the final statement of *al sein Jahr* to set up a strong cadence to tonic with a trill on the leading tone before finishing out the aria alone (bars 17–20). The oboe plays an important role in this aria, ranging from adding emphasis to individual words to driving the interest of the

voice's repetitions. In collaboration with the basso continuo, it becomes a representation of Darius's pain, literally preventing him from finding resolution. Even more so than in Kusser's solo writing for the instrument, the oboe is here an expressive partner to the voice. This practice of beginning with the oboe before trading off short statements which then develop into a simultaneous interaction between the two parts was Keiser's most common use of the solo oboe in his operas.

The image displays a musical score for three systems. The first system features a Hautbois Solo part with a trill (tr) and a Cyrene part. The second system includes an Oboe (Ob.) part with a trill (tr), a C part with the lyrics 'Kein Mensch siegt ü-ber sei-ne', and a B.C. part with a trill (tr). The third system shows an Oboe (Ob.) part with a trill (tr), a C part with the lyrics 'See - le, siegt ü - ber sei - ne See - le kein', and a B.C. part. The score is written in 4/4 time with a key signature of one flat.

Example 4 - Reinhard Keiser. *Nebucadnezar*, 'Kein Mensch siegt über Seine Seele' (Act II, Scene 12, bars 1–7).

³⁹ Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 315.

What Handel learned in Hamburg

Hautbois Solo

Darius

B.C.

Ob.

D

B.C.

Lieb-es -

Krank - heit Lie - bes - Krank - heit hat Ge - fahr

Example 5 - Reinhard Keiser. *Nebucadnezar*, 'Liebes krankheit' (Act III, Scene 12, bars 1–5).

10

Hautbois Solo

Darius

B.C.

H.S.

D

B.C.

H.S.

D

B.C.

zu - wei - len, sich zu hei - len, müs - se mehr sein als ein Jahr, müs - se

mehr sein als ein Jahr als ein Jahr

als ein Jahr als ein Jahr. dass zu - wei - len, sich zu hei - len, müs - se mehr sein als ein Jahr.

Example 6 - Reinhard Keiser. *Nebucadnezar*, 'Liebes krankheit' (Act III, Scene 12, bars 10–17).

Discerning a Collective Style

These three operas display a number of common elements in their writing for the oboe. Arias with solo oboe obbligatos are generally in quadruple metre but sometimes in triple and can be in either a major or minor key, depending upon the affect of the text. The concerted aria is the most common accompaniment type, though Keiser's realization of this often begins as a prelude-ritornel before combining the voice and oboe, a practice Handel often adopted in his own arias. In these arias, the oboe line is nearly always drawn from the vocal melody. Arias with two oboe lines are in the prelude-ritornel style and are more variable in terms of metre, using duple, triple, or quadruple. This type is most often used for more cheerful affects and so is often in a major key.

As shown, the obbligato oboe, particularly in laments such as Kusser's 'Ach daß doch meine Pein' and Keiser's 'Liebes krankheit' is neither an idle member of the ripieno nor an impartial observer. Rather, it is an extension of the voice; one half of an expressive unit. The effectiveness of this combination was noted by audience members who were struck by the integration of oboe and voice in Keiser's operas. One such patron wrote that 'arias were composed especially to be declaimed in an opera using a single hautboy and a single female voice. They were charming, and the sound of the voice and instrument blended together so well that it seemed but a single voice.'⁴⁰ The appeal of arias for oboe and voice (for composers and audience members) would have lain in both the ability of the oboe to emulate the voice and in its own distinct qualities. Unburdened by text, the oboe may freely shift between adding emphasis in solidarity with its vocal counterpart and taking up the melody when the singer is without words. Unlike the voice, the oboe's power to impart meaning is not in declaration, but suggestion. While the vocalist's emotions are conveyed through the text, the oboist must draw the listener in simply through their expression of the aria's affect. As Geoffrey Burgess put it: '[...] the oboe's very inability to convey linguistic meaning is what also allows it to transcend words and communicate more directly through

emotion.'⁴¹ These qualities are likely what drew Conradi and Kusser to utilize the oboe as a solo instrument in their operas, setting an example for the composers who followed them, particularly Keiser and Handel.

Ultimately, the style that had developed in Hamburg by the first years of the eighteenth century was codified by Keiser. However, it was strongly colored by the influence of Conradi and Kusser's earlier writing for the oboe, both in the more objective areas of metre and key area and in the relationship between voice and oboe. This influence ranges from Conradi's separation of the two to Kusser's move toward an integration of the oboe as a partner to the voice and often as an extension of the character it accompanies. My analysis of Handel's first opera will demonstrate ways in which he both benefited from and contributed to this style.

Obbligatos in Handel's First Opera, 1705

While accounts differ on the details of the events leading up to the premier of Handel's first opera, all frame it as a precipitous moment for the young composer. With Keiser away for much of the season, the theatre in need of a new opera, and Mattheson's *Cleopatra* having been premiered only the month before, Handel was granted his big break: the opportunity to write and stage his first opera. The similarities between Handel's use of the oboe in *Almira* and the operas discussed previously are considerable and suggest a familiarity with previous Hamburg operas (Table 6).⁴² As David Hunter has suggested, Handel would have had '[...] unfettered access to the opera house library' in Keiser's absence and the opportunity to study previous operas as he undertook the composition of his first.⁴³ Similarities can certainly be seen in the correlation between the keys and metres of Handel's arias with those of Keiser's from the same categories (see tables 5 and 6). Beyond the similarities in his use of the oboe, Handel's familiarity with previous Hamburg operas is evident in his adoption of the distinct mix of styles practiced at the opera.

⁴⁰ Denis Nolhac, *Voilage historique et politique* (Frankfurt, 1737), II: 166, translated in Haynes, *The Eloquent Oboe*, 138.

⁴¹ Burgess and Haynes, *The Oboe*, 234.

⁴² George Frideric Handel, *Almira* (Leipzig: Deutsche Händelgesellschaft, 1873).

⁴³ Hunter, *The Lives of George Frideric Handel*, 221.

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Aria Title	Category	Subcategory	Parts	Voice Type	Tempo	Metre	Key
'Chi piu mi piace'	1	1a	1 oboe line and continuo	Soprano	N/A	4/4	C Minor
'Geloso tormento'	1	1b	1 oboe line, strings, and continuo	Soprano	N/A	4/4	E Minor
'Lass ein sanftes'	2	2	2 oboe lines and continuo	Bass	N/A	3/4	D Minor
'Kommt, vermehrt'	2	1a	2 oboe lines and continuo	Tenor	N/A	4/4	G Minor
'Gönne nach'	1	2	1 oboe line and continuo	Bass	N/A	4/4	C Minor
'Spielet ihr'	3	1a	Unison oboe line and separate unison violin line	Soprano and Tenor	N/A	6/8	B-flat Major

Table 6 - Characteristics of Handel's Arias with Obligato Oboe(s) in *Almira* (1705)

Handel included the most extensive use of the oboe seen thus far in 'Geloso tormento', a lament from act 1 in which *Almira* languishes in her mistaken belief that *Fernando* loves another.

Geloso tormento
Mi va rodendo il cor.
Non dite, che vile
Quest' anima sia,
Ch' il morir di gelosia
Tra le morti e la peggior.

Jealous torment
Gnaws at my heart.
Do not say that mine is a
Contemptible soul,
For to die of jealousy
Is the worst death of all!⁴⁴

From the very beginning of this aria, Handel creates an atmosphere of unrelenting distress, '[...] a tension that is not permitted to relax' as Winton Dean and John Merrill Knapp wrote (Ex. 7).⁴⁵ Handel creates this tension through sudden shifts in dynamic and a semiquaver motive in which the strings hammer out loud repetitions of seventh chords. Over top of this, the oboe is given an extensive opening solo made up of sorrowful descending figures, repetitions of pitches, and sudden bursts of fast notes. Given the dramatic nature of the oboe line, the listener might expect similarly dramatic writing for the voice, but *Almira* is largely more restrained aside from a brief flourish in bar 11. Whereas the oboe is situated almost entirely above the staff, near the top of its range for instruments of the time, Handel often keeps the voice within the staff. Handel utilizes the oboe here as a separate incarnation of *Almira*; it expresses the same affect but through a contrasting style. *Almira*

herself is more restrained rhythmically, suggesting a more withdrawn and defeated mindset. Alongside her, the oboe hints at the more extreme dimensions of her emotional state through a simplified version of its original melody. This points back to the opening's more dramatic presentation of the melody without overshadowing *Almira*. Handel's use of the oboe in this aria is both a reflection of the oboe's reliance on affect as necessitated by its lack of text and of Handel's use of the instrument to more fully portray the range of *Almira*'s emotions.

In the Act III aria 'Gönne nach', Handel pairs the solo oboe with a male voice, breaking from the norm in Hamburg in which arias for male voice had generally been paired with two oboes (see tables 3-5). Taking place after *Edilia*'s lament earlier in the scene, 'Gönne nach' is presented as *Raymondo*'s attempt to comfort her while also seeking her affection.

Gönne nach den Thränen Güssen
Mir nur einen Gnaden Blick;
Laß die Sonne,
Deiner Wonne,
Mein so oft verlangtes Glück,
Mit geneigten Strahlen grüssen;
Gönne nach den Thränen Güssen
Mir nur einen Gnaden Blick!

Grant me, after those tears are gone,
One gracious glance;
Let the sun
Of your delight,
My longed-for happiness,
Greet me with its kindly rays.
Grant me, after those tears are gone,
One gracious glance.⁴⁶

⁴⁴ Friedrich Christian Feustking, *Almira, Königin von Castilien* (Hamburg: 1704), translated in Matthias Zins and Gilbert Blin, liner notes to *George Frideric Handel: Almira*, Paul O'Dette, Stephen Stubbs and Boston Early Music Festival, CPO 555205-2, CD, 2019, 86.

⁴⁵ Winton Dean and John Merrill Knapp, *Handel's Operas: 1704–1726* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1987), 58–59.

⁴⁶ Feustking, *Almira*, in Zins and Blin, liner notes to *George Frideric Handel: Almira*, 120.

The musical score is arranged in systems. The first system includes Hautb. Solo, Almira, Violin I, Violin II, Viola, and Bassi. The second system includes H.S., Al., Vln. I, Vln. II, Vla., and B. The Hautb. Solo part features a prominent descending melodic line with dynamic markings of *f*, *p*, and *f*. The strings provide a rhythmic accompaniment with dynamic markings of *p* and *f*. The vocal line (Al.) enters in the second system with the lyrics 'Ge - lo - so tor - men - to ge - lo - so tor - men - to mi'.

Example 7 - George Frideric Handel. *Almira*, 'Geloso tormento' (Act I, Scene 6, bars 1-9).

Through its minor tonality, descending motives, and frequent half steps, 'Gönne nach' is not the aria one would expect upon reading the text (ex. 8). Rather, Handel's setting implies an additional layer of meaning beyond that found in the text, providing a glimpse into Raymondo's emotional state following his earlier rejection by Almira. In the A section, Raymondo repeats the first two lines of text, 'Grant me, after those tears are gone, one gracious glance', five times. After the first

statement, the subsequent four are delivered without pause, giving the sense of Raymondo pleading with Edilia. The obbligato is largely in the prelude-ritornel style, including only one significant combination of oboe and voice. The oboe sets up the rolling descending motive which the voice later takes up, but the melody here is less flowing than when sung by Raymondo, including pauses and more quavers which offer a break between strings of semiquavers. This makes

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Hautb. Solo

Raymondo

Bassi

H.S.

R.

B.

Gön-ne nach den Thrän-en güs-sen mir nur ei-nen Gna-den blick,

H.S.

R.

B.

gön-ne nach den Thrän-en - güs-sen mir nur ei-nen Gna-den

Example 8 - George Frideric Handel. *Almira*, 'Gönne nach' (Act III, Scene 5, bars 1–10).

Raymondo's first statement appears as a more complete thought, having been previously worked out in the oboe's line. Raymondo's second phrase, while utilizing more quavers than the first, includes large intervallic leaps in contrast to the oboe's largely scalar quavers. This style of writing maintains Handel's close association of oboe and voice, presenting them as two incarnations of a single character, this time with Raymondo being more emotive than the oboe in contrast with the opposite having been used in Almira's aria. By keeping the statements of the voice and oboe largely separate, Handel emphasized the differences in their delivery of the melody.

The four operas analyzed throughout this article reflect an evolution of the ways in which the oboe was utilized for the operas of the Oper am Gänsemarkt. From Conradi's two oboes to Handel's extensive solo lines, the oboe was a significant presence in Hamburg operas at the turn of the eighteenth century. While records do not exist to confirm the identities of the oboists employed at the opera, these obligatos are a testament to the considerable abilities of these performers. The obligatos written before Handel's *Almira* contain many similarities in metre, tonality, and style of accompaniment which made

their way into Handel's own writing for the instrument, both in *Almira* and in his later operas. In her *Feminine Endings*, Susan McClary writes, 'for if the glory of opera is its ability to give the illusion of depth to characters (i.e., to deliver both verbal text and also an additional dimension that inflects the text affectively), then a great deal depends on who seems to be wielding that second dimension.'⁴⁷ In the operas discussed here, these four composers set a precedent for the use of the oboe as this second dimension, demonstrating its effectiveness as an extension of the singer, whether male or female. This practice continued to be a major influence on Handel throughout his career, as he would go on to write a number of obbligatos for the instrument. As my analysis has shown, he made his own contributions to this received style, but the foundations of his use of the oboe are found in Hamburg operas such as those discussed here. As John Butt put it, Handel did not '[...] miraculously spring fully formed into cosmopolitan musical life [...]' but was influenced by the music and composers with which he interacted throughout his travels.⁴⁸

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⁴⁷ Susan McClary, *Feminine Endings: Music, Gender, and Sexuality* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2002), 46.

⁴⁸ John Butt, 'Germany—education and apprenticeship', *The Cambridge Companion to Handel*, ed. Burrows, 11.

Blurred Boundaries

Performance through Transcription in Edwin Fischer's Bach Recordings

Pierre Riley

Edwin Fischer holds a unique place in the history of Bach performance and its twentieth-century reception: under his fingers, the *Well-Tempered Clavier* was committed in its entirety to wax and shellac for the first time. The recording, released in instalments between 1934 and 1937, spent several years as the only complete set available and has never spent any significant length of time out of print.¹ As a result, Fischer exerted considerable influence on the reception of the work, first as the progenitor of a benchmark performance, but also, with the passing of years, as the witness of a bygone era. By the end of his life, Fischer was among a dwindling number of pianists whose musical mindset had fully formed in the time before the outbreak of the First World War, when Brahms's late works counted as contemporary, and the careers of Clara Schumann and Liszt were still vividly alive in musicians' collective memory. He was steeped in a multi-faceted ideal of musicianship that meant that his activities as a pianist and conductor were enriched by the practice of arrangement, improvisation, and composition.

Fischer's recorded performances cry out for closer analysis because we can glean from them critical insights about how scores were understood in ways that differ from the commonly held knowledge of the present – both in terms of the end result, and in terms of the philosophical preconceptions about the relationship between scores and performance. Fischer's recordings show that a characteristic feature of his performance approach was to navigate deftly between – and to a certain extent merge – two activities that we understand today as separate and qualitatively different forms of musical labour: transcription and performance. Fischer's case stands to illuminate how the ostensibly work-fixated attitudes on display in his

writings actually support rather than hinder the imaginative and profoundly creative performances we hear in his recordings.

I begin by summarising some of Fischer's intellectual influences, which will provide essential context for his own pronouncements and recorded performances. I then explore how his use of editions and his approach to reading Bach's text are coloured by a hermeneutically strong idea of textual scholarship. Finally, the continuities and contiguities between performance and transcription in Fischer's recordings are described and discussed in detail.

Scylla and Charybdis: A Dialectical Approach in Practice

Let us begin by inviting Fischer to speak on his own behalf. The following quotation is indicative of Fischer's persistent habit of confronting seemingly contradictory dyads in search for some kind of conciliatory synthesis:

There are two dangerous paths open to the performer: one in which one's own passions commandeer [the composer's] musical idiom to express themselves, and the other, in which the player simply reproduces slavishly the notes and directions on the score. One must constantly manoeuvre between this Scylla and Charybdis, avoiding both immoderate self-portrayal, and petrified respect.²

This is more than a stylistic quirk of his prose. The process of navigating between Scylla and Charybdis appears as a theme in much of his artistic output. Fischer will even *seem* to contradict himself, but closer analysis reveals how productively these ostensible contradictions can

¹ It is unclear how late His Master's Voice continued manufacturing the 78rpm discs, but reissues in the new long-playing 33 $\frac{1}{3}$ rpm format were released in 1957. See Roger Smithson, 'Edwin Fischer: A Chronological Discography', online, <https://www.thepianofiles.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/Edwin-Fischer-Discography-by-Roger-Smithson-2019-3-29.pdf> (accessed 11 August 2023).

² 'Zwei gefährliche Wege öffnen sich dem Nachgestalter: einer, auf dem die eigene Leidenschaft sich der Beethovenschen Tonsprache bedient, um sich selbst darzustellen, der andere, auf dem der Spieler einfach sklavisch alles befolgt, was ihm auszuführen in den Notenzeichen vorgeschrieben ist. Zwischen dieser Szylla und Charybdis hat man hindurch zu steuern: weder Maßlos sich selbst darzustellen, noch in zu großem Respekt zu versteinen.' [My translation] Edwin Fischer, *Ludwig van Beethovens Klaviersonaten: Ein Begleiter für Studierende und Liebhaber* (Wiesbaden: Insel-Verlag, 1956), 14.

be. His writings and his activity as performer all bear witness to an attempt – or a lifelong series of attempts – to grapple with a question that has not lost any of its urgency: that of approaching the past without erasing the present. As I will demonstrate in this article, Fischer’s solutions to this conundrum involved thinking about performance in a way that was fundamentally informed in its basic premises by the idea of what we would now call “transcription,” and nurtured by a blurring of boundaries between these two ostensibly different activities.

Intellectual Influences

Fischer’s extant writings have an unceremoniously refined erudition. The bulk of this corpus consists of editions and prefaces, as well as transcripts of addresses given to students in the context of masterclasses. Even the more systematic written sources, like his *Reflections on Music* or the Beethoven companion quoted above, are the result of reworking and enlarging notes from ‘live’ musical encounters such as the music academies at which he taught in Potsdam and later Lausanne. He seems to have delighted in the exchange of ideas he had with younger musicians during the many masterclasses he taught.³ In his own words, Fischer tends to use the rhetorical tone of homilies on artistic integrity. They are approachable and, though often practically helpful, tend to dwell on elucidating artistry through historical, artistic, and philosophical vantage points.

Fischer’s injunctions addressed to students will be familiar to any musician with formal training, so familiar, in fact, that they may appear routine. But this advice bears witness to a network of intellectual influences, not least of which is a tradition of philosophical idealism and dialectical thinking. His connections to the intellectual life of fin-de-siècle and Weimar-era Berlin were personal as well as professional. Through one of his first students, he was welcomed into the capital’s salon society,⁴ where he frequented not only of artists

and intellectuals – Joachim, Busoni, Reger, Schweitzer, Bertholet – but also influential personalities from the world of banking and philanthropy, such as Franz von Mendelssohn.⁵ In 1919, Fischer married Franz’s niece Eleonora. By marrying into the Mendelssohn family, writes Christian Schaper, Fischer had joined an already venerable institution of German high culture:

As Fischer later freely admitted, without the social advantages of entering an aristocratic family and the contacts such a union brought with it, a pianist of comparable diligence and talent might not have achieved as much as he did. As it was, he became the most important representative of the Berlin circle next to Artur Schnabel, and Wilhelm Furtwängler’s favourite pianist into the bargain.⁶

Although evidently not necessarily *of* the exalted, quasi-aristocratic milieu of Berlin’s intelligentsia, he was unquestionably welcomed into it.

Two pieces of evidence tie Fischer to an *intellectual* rather than artistic milieu. He is credited, along with Paul Dikenmann, for compiling the index in Ernst Kurth’s last work, *Musikpsychologie*, which appeared in 1931.⁷ Although posterity did not bestow upon Kurth the same institutionally canonised status as his contemporary Heinrich Schenker, he was a highly influential musical thinker in his day and in the German-speaking world and a disciple of Guido Adler.⁸ He was among a group of analysts whose practice was retroactively described as ‘energeticism’. His writings treated music as a dynamically unfolding process, with harmony as well as melody reflecting pent up forces: ‘Kurth posits such a motive force to be psychological – a kind of psychic energy. A composer’s psychic flow, embodied in the music, manifests itself primarily in melody, notably in “linear” counterpoint’ such as Bach’s.⁹ His *Grundlagen des linearen Kontrapunkts* treated the counterpoint of Bach as animated by the linear

³ Edwin Fischer, *Von den Aufgaben des Musikers* (Wiesbaden: Insel-Verlag, 1960), 20.

⁴ Jürgen Schmidt-Voigt, ‘Musikalische Begegnungen’, in *Dank an Edwin Fischer*, ed. Hugo Haid (Wiesbaden: F. A. Brockhaus, 1961), 30.

⁵ Bradley Brookshire, ‘Edwin Fischer’s Bach-Pianism in Context’, *Understanding Bach* 11 (2016): 108, 111.

⁶ Christian Schaper, Liner notes for *The Welte Mignon Mystery Vol. 17: Edwin Fischer Today Playing all his 1923 (1909?) Interpretations*, Edwin Fischer (piano), recorded c.1909–2010, Tacet Musikproduktion TACET181DIG, Audio CD, 2010, 8.

⁷ Ernst Kurth, *Musikpsychologie* (Berlin: Max Hesses Verlag, 1931), 318; Brookshire, ‘Fischer’s Bach Pianism’, 109.

⁸ See Ernst Kurth, *Selected Writings*, ed. and trans. Lee Rothfarb (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press: 1991), 1–34.

⁹ Lee Rothfarb, ‘Energetics’, in *The Cambridge History of Western Music Theory*, ed. Thomas Christensen (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2002), 929.

motion of melody. The idea of musical forces moving, as it were, underneath the surface-level features, had direct consequences for other activities this article will scrutinise. Thomas Christensen relates how Kurth happily performed four-hand arrangements of Bruckner's Symphonies: 'far from being a regrettable last resort, a well-performed piano arrangement was, Kurth thought, infinitely preferable to a badly executed orchestral performance led by a conductor with no empathy for the music.'¹⁰ He and Edwin Fischer, both born in 1886, are known to have been well-acquainted, and some sources¹¹ even suggest that Fischer was a pupil of Kurth. That Fischer was familiar Kurth's work can, at any rate, be in no doubt. As will be seen below, a philosophical commitment to the idea of 'the music itself' is manifest in Fischer's writings and, more importantly, in his practice.

Almost at the same time, Fischer oversaw the publication of Max Schlesinger's *Symbolik in der Tonkunst*. The work had been planned as the eighth part of Schlesinger's magnum opus, *Die Geschichte des Symbols*,¹² which endeavoured to develop a comprehensive exploration of symbolism. This was undertaken with a staggeringly broad historical and anthropological focus, encompassing literature, architecture, law, religion, and even some psychoanalytic influences, in addition to the more familiar avenues of representative art. The completion of the final part, about sound and symbolism, was interrupted by Schlesinger's death in 1915. Fischer's brief preface states that the author had left him a nearly finished manuscript in 1914, and that he had 'ordered and collected' the papers in preparation for publication. He adds (somewhat vaguely) that 'the introductions to some of the chapters are by the editor'.¹³ In the general introduction, summarising Schlesinger's approach

in the first seven parts of the *Symbolik* and detailing how the general framework would be applied to music, the reader encounters a familiar refrain of idealist thought: 'Every symbol consists of two parts, two "symbol-halves": the tangible, present *image* [*Abbild*] and the more abstract, invisible *archetype* [*Urbild*].'¹⁴ The preface continues by outlining the challenges of applying to musical features the study of symbolic meaning, how this 'way of meaning' emerges from allusive resemblance rather than mimetic resemblance.¹⁵

Although most of Fischer's writings were addressed to friends, students, and a general public of music lovers, it is likely that he was expertly acquainted these musicological and philosophical areas in relation to his practice. The connections with Kurth and Schlesinger both help situate Fischer in an analytical tradition influenced by energeticism (and, to a degree, organicism) and more broadly in an intellectual tradition shaped by idealist thought.

Approaches to the Work and Approaches to the Past

Fischer seemed careful to separate out notions of score, work, and performance. He nevertheless insisted on a methodical and disciplined approach to the printed text when learning repertoire:

The score handed down to us presents itself as a clear, well-developed floor plan, with some indications as to the use of materials and interior decoration, but after all only a floor plan. *We* must build it – let us consider it our highest duty to build exactly according to the plan, to allow no alterations, neither in quantity nor in form,

¹⁰ Thomas Christensen, 'Four-Hand Piano Transcription and Geographies of Nineteenth-Century Musical Reception', *Journal of the American Musicological Society* 52/2 (1999): 264.

¹¹ Daphne Tan, 'Ernst Kurth at the Boundary of Music Theory and Psychology', PhD dissertation, University of Rochester (2013), 26 note 37. See also Brookshire, 'Fischer's Bach Pianism', 109 note 5 and corresponding passage.

¹² Edwin Fischer, Preface to 'Symbolik in der Tonkunst', in Max Schlesinger, *Geschichte des Symbols: Ein Versuch* (Hildesheim: G. Olms Verlag, [1930] 1967), 3.

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ 'Besteht jedes symbol aus zwei Teilen, zwei Symbolhälften, dem faßbaren, anwesenden *Abbild* und dem meist abstrakten unsichtbaren *Urbild*.' [My translation; italics in original] Max Schlesinger, *Symbolik in der Tonkunst* (Hildesheim: G. Olms Verlag [1930] 1967), 7.

¹⁵ It is noteworthy that Fischer's two forays into academic publications tie energeticism and the study of symbols. Rothfarb notes how 'the attraction of symbolist ideas to the energeticists should be clear. If the idea of concrete mimetic content in music proved precarious (whether of specific images or generalized affections), a symbolic interpretation might offer a way of rescuing music from sheer formalism.'

Rothfarb, 'Energetics', 929.

to add nothing, but to build as *beautifully* and with as good material as possible.¹⁶

Then again, he complained that scores in and of themselves could not be considered identical to either works or performances, subjected as they are to the limitations of notation. Certain passages betray an open ambivalence about scores themselves:

The score is also an enemy of our music-making. What once appeared radiant and resounding in the breast of the artist, what once welled up so warmly in the heart, is, when written down, regimented into bars and beats, constricted into three or four dynamic levels, and given only a few rudimentary expressive indications. And how many nuances there are, for phrasing or emphasising different bars. So forget about bar lines – instead, breathe and sing melodies.¹⁷

The import of such a turn of phrase – describing the score as an *enemy* of music-making – cannot be overstated, even if one allows for the exigencies of rhetorical effect.¹⁸ Fischer is therefore also leading us to the conclusion that that, even though it is not perfectly or entirely encapsulated in the score, there is *something* out there that the performer is duty-bound to render according to plan.

He stopped short of accepting a definition of the work that would encase it into a static existence – as a repository of immanent and unchanging meaning to be divined by exegesis. Fischer compared the experience of the masterwork to that of an awe-inspiring landscape, on which changing light and weather project an infinite variety of

characters. About the musical masterpiece, he concludes:

Such a work says something different every time: today it echoes with the storm and stress of our lives; tomorrow, it yields to logical analysis. Should you ask colours of it, it has them; should you want pure, architectonic forms, you find them, and, stricken with awe, you contemplate the mysterious enigma of these works, in which so much diversity is concentrated, and which have so many facets.¹⁹

One can never see all its facets at the same time. With this comes the implication that different performances of the work can be equally truthful – or, at the very least, no *single* performance can claim to be final and authoritative. Fischer's advice to students illustrates fervently how a performance must have a living, dynamically unfolding quality:

At the origin of all creative activity, stands that primal feeling, which, tied to no specific sense, derives from the most fundamental vital processes. *Tension* and *relaxation*, pressure and release, *inhaling* and *exhaling*, already harbour within themselves two key elements of the art of music, dissonance and consonance, and in their alternation, 'rhythm'... All elements of music – melody, rhythm, harmony, tonality, cadence, and form – are alive with the eternal alternation of *inhaling* and *exhaling*, day and night, loud and soft, high and low, rising and falling, entanglement and release.²⁰

¹⁶ 'So stellt sich nun das überlieferte Notenbild als ein zwar ausgearbeiteter, deutlicher Grundriß mit Angaben über Materialverwendung, geplante Innenausstattung dar, aber eben doch nur als Grundriß – gebaut muß von *uns* werden –; wir wollen es als unsere größte Pflicht betrachten, genau nach dem Grundriß zu bauen, und keine Änderungen weder in den Maßen noch Formen zu gestatten, nichts hinzuzutun, aber so *schön*, mit so gutem Material wie irgend möglich zu bauen.' [My translation; Fischer's italics]. Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 27.

¹⁷ 'Ein Feind unseres Musizierens ist auch die Notenschrift. Was einst im Busen des Künstlers leuchtend, tönend erschien, was einst so heiß dem Herzen entquoll, wird beim Niederschreiben in Takte gepreßt, in drei bis vier Stärkegrade eingeschnürt, und mit einigen wenigen Vortragsangaben versehen. Und wie viele Nuancen gibt es, wie verschiedenen können Takte phrasiert, betont werden. Also halte dich nicht an die Taktstrichgitterstäbe, sondern atme, singe Melodien.' [My translation]. Fischer, *Aufgaben*, 17–18.

¹⁸ It should be noted that this quotation appears in Fischer's last dated work – published the year before his death. It is not out of the question that, by 1960, Fischer's earlier injunctions to scrupulous score-fidelity no longer needed quite the same level of advocacy, and that he found the need to emphasise freedom and spontaneity in the postwar climate of modernism in performance approach.

¹⁹ 'Ein solches Werk sagt jedesmal etwas anderes aus: es faßt heute unseren Lebenssturm, un läßt sich morgen logisch auslegen; verlangst Du Farben von ihm, es hat sie, willst Du reine, architektonische Formen, Du findest sie und staunend betrachtest Du das geheimnisvolle Rätsel dieser Werke, in denen so konzentriert ein Vielfaches ist, und die so viele Gesichte haben.' [My Translation] Edwin Fischer, *Johann Sebastian Bach: Eine Studie* (Potsdam: Offizin Eduard Stichnote, 1943), 37.

²⁰ 'Am Anfang alles schöpferischen Geschehens steht wohl jenes Urgefühl, das, an kein bestimmtes Sinnesorgan gebunden, sich aus primitivsten Lebensvorgängen ableitet. *Spannung* und *Entspannung*, Druck und Befreiung, Ein- und Ausatmen bergen in sich schon zwei

The alternation of tension and release pervades his pronouncements about performing. When he asked what it means, exactly, to be 'musical', he answered that such a quality resides not in the ability to render sequences of tones or beats, but in a feeling for the tensions that exist between them, and a sensitivity to the organising principles in the score that marshal the notes into musical events. The same concern for tension and release lead him to distinguish between time (*Takt*) and rhythm: 'time is vertical; rhythm is horizontal. ... Rhythm is the force that comes from the relationship between what comes before and what comes after, hence building tension'.²¹ What we see here is nothing less than a practically-oriented musician's response to the body of work of Ernst Kurth.

Fischer's approach to the past is shaped by similar ambivalences to the one governing his idea of the work, in which the performer is unquestionably laden with duties and responsibilities, but the performer's loyalty is pledged not to anything as prosaic as restoration *wie es eigentlich war*. Instead, he urged students to sympathetically imagine the past in which Bach lived. In his essay on Bach, he posited that,

To understand a historically great personality, to interpret his works correctly, one must also comprehend the environment in which it found itself. One must accomplish the difficult task of banishing from the mind everything material and spiritual that did not yet exist, that had not yet been discovered or written,

or had not yet occurred. In our case, then, to understand Bach in his time, we must dispense with Haydn, Mozart, Beethoven, and all the romantics, but also all the freethinking philosophy of later generations, their political ideas and their ways of conceiving of space around them. On the other hand, one must retrieve everything that, to us, has vanished into the shadows of the past, but was still visible and potent during his lifetime: the religiosity of his epoch, its symbolism, its tight bond to the church. Only then do we understand the Master not only from our perspective, but in an objective sense.²²

Fischer could but only be conscious of the historical contingency of his views: seeming to espouse the opposite opinion only four years earlier, he recognised that it takes creative force to give life to works that are centuries old, and that even the most objective approach will be coloured by the artist's subjective prerogatives:

Objectivity is in fact an absurdity, because what has not gone through my senses, what has not gone through my mind, simply *isn't*. A so-called objective representation is, in its basis, a subjective one. 'Objective' is often called 'faithful to the work' [*Werktreu*], and this is actually a beautiful word. But it must not be understood as 'true to the outer signs', or 'true to the printer's ink', but it must be true to the force of the effect within.²³

Hauptelemente der Tonkunst, Dissonanz und Konsonanz, und in ihrem Wechsel den »rhythmus« ... Alle elemente der Tonkunst, die Melodie, der Rhythmus, die Harmonie, die Tonalität, die Kadenz, die Form, leben von diesem ewigen Wechsel von Ein- und Ausatmen von Tag und Nacht, Laut und Leise, Hoch und Tief, Anschwellen und Abnehmen, Sich-Verwickeln und Sich-Lösen.' Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 23–24. (Fischer's italics).

²¹ 'Takt ist das, was senkrecht ist, Rhythmus ist horizontal. Anders ausgedrückt: der Takt nimmt keine Rücksicht auf das, was vorher and nachher ist. Der Rhythmus ist die Kraft, die in Beziehung steht zum Vorher and Nachher, also eine Spannungsfunktion. Das gibt den Unterschied am besten wieder.' [My translation] Edwin Fischer, 'Auszüge aus einem Stenogramm des Meisterkurses Potsdam 1936 von Paul Reuschel', in *Dank an Edwin Fischer*, ed. Hugo Haid (Wiesbaden: F. A. Brockhaus, 1961): 64.

²² 'Um eine geschichtlich große Persönlichkeit zu begreifen, um deren Werke richtig zu interpretieren, muß man auch die Umwelt erfassen, in die sie hineingestellt war; man muß das Schwerige fertigbringen, sich all das an Geschaffenem und Geistigem fortzudenken, was vor ihm noch nicht existierte, nicht gefunden, geschrieben und geschehen war. In unserem Falle also müssen wir um Bach in seiner Zeit zu erfassen, alle Musik von Haydn, Mozart, Beethoven, die ganze Romantik, aber auch alle Philosophie und Freigeisterei, die politischen und Raumbegriffe der späteren Generationen ausschalten. Man muß andererseits alles wieder herausholen, was für uns im Dunkel der Vergangenheit verschwand, zu seiner Lebenszeit aber noch sichtbar und wirksam war: die Religiosität seiner Epoche, ihre Symbolik, ihre kirchliche Gebundenheit. Erst dann verstehen wir den Meister nicht nur von uns aus, sondern im objektiven Sinne.' [My translation] Fischer, *Bach*, 30–31.

²³ 'Eigentlich ist Objektivität ein Nonsens, denn was nicht durch meine Sinne, durch meinen Geist gegangen ist, existiert nicht, *ist* nicht! Also ist auch eine sogenannte objektive Darstellung im Grunde eine subjektive. Objektiv nennt man Werktru, und dies ist eigentlich ein schönes Wort. Es darf aber nicht verstanden werden als treu den äußeren Zeichen, der Druckerschwärze treu, sondern treu den darüber

Fischer added that ‘we are also people of our own time’, cautioning that many external conventions existed only as a result of deeply internalised behaviours that might be totally foreign to the modern observer, implying that what we do now still needs to have some connection to an inner logic, inevitably, our own.²⁴ He recognised that a musician’s performance will inevitably be coloured by the spirit of his or her time, and he expressed the belief that ‘the interpreter cannot escape from his own personality’, conditioned as it is by the musician’s education, environment, and physiognomy.²⁵

Fischer’s close juxtaposition of the terms *Werktreue* and “true to the printer’s ink” is revealing of a persistent habit among musicians of Fischer’s generation of balancing faithfulness to the text against faithfulness to its spirit, inaccessible and distant as it may be. Hans-Joachim Hinrichsen identifies Wagner as one of the significant champions in the nineteenth century of this still current idea. On his approach to Beethoven, Hinrichsen writes:

Significantly, Wagner’s justification for his interpretation is identical to an appeal to the composer’s will... It was, so to speak, a moral duty to do in the present what the composer would have done if he were still alive... To this day, the argument that has been derived from this issue is that performers – from their contemporary perspective – must defend the spirit of the work against its letter. Often enough, this is exactly the reasoning through which

deviation from the text is nonetheless legitimised as fulfilling the composer’s will. Of course, the difference between spirit and letter, between meaning and text, is a fundamental, generative tension in the performer’s work in general. Of course, faithfulness to the work and faithfulness to the text are two different aspects of interpretation, but they can hardly be played off against each other in the sense of deciding one way or another.²⁶

The legitimising of “deviance”, as Hinrichsen puts it, went hand in hand with the practice of score-reading at the piano as an access point for understanding a composer’s style. In fact, Wagner’s encounter with Beethoven, Christensen adds, was mediated by the piano:

There are few better means of getting to know a score well than having to translate it into the medium of the piano. Wagner claimed that the best composition lesson he received as a youth was that of transcribing Beethoven’s Ninth Symphony for the instrument. To this day, the practice of *Partiturspiel* – sight-reading orchestral scores at the keyboard – is still prescribed in many curricula as an aid to learning orchestration and conducting.²⁷

According to Hinrichsen, the idea ‘that a musical performance would be described or even perceived as an interpretation [in the sense that legal and biblical exegeses are interpretative, the author later clarifies] is a relatively recent phenomenon, which has gradually gained acceptance since the mid-

wirkenden Kräften.’ [My translation; Fischer’s italics] Fischer, ‘Ansprache vom 2. Juli 1939 bei Eröffnung der Meisterkurse des Deutschen Musikinstituts für Ausländer in Potsdam’, in *Dank an Edwin Fischer*, ed. Hugo Haid (Wiesbaden: F. A. Brockhaus, 1961): 60.

²⁴ ‘Aber wir sind auch Menschen dieser Zeit. Die Sitten sind nicht nur äußerlich, sondern auch ein innerlicher Vorgang. Dazu gehören zum Beispiel die Höflichkeit und die äußeren Formen am Hofe Ludwigs XIV., wo es eine Beleidigung war, nach der falschen Seite eine Referenz zu machen. Man versuche auch diese Dinge in der Auffassung des Werkes zu berücksichtigen. Darf sich aber nicht auf die Zeit des Niederschreibens beschränken, sondern muß den geistigen Zustand der Schöpfers in Betracht ziehen. Beethoven ist manchmal ganz modern, die heutigen sind manchmal ganz alt, man muß irgendeine Stilleinheit finden und dann diesen Stilcharakter durchhalten.’ Fischer, ‘Auszüge aus einem Stenogramm’, 68–69.

²⁵ Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 31–32.

²⁶ Wagners Begründung seiner Interpretation ist bezeichnenderweise identisch mit der Berufung auf den Willen des Komponisten... Es sei gewissermaßen eine moralische Pflicht, in der Gegenwart das zu tun, was der Komponist, würde er noch leben, ebenfalls getan hätte... Bis heute wird aus der darlegenden Problematik das Argument gewonnen, der Interpret habe – aus seiner jeweils zeitgenössischen Perspektive – den Geist des Werkes gegen seinen Buchstaben zu verteidigen. Oft genug ist genau dies das Argument, mit dem das abweichen vom Text dennoch als Erfüllung des Komponisten-Willens legitimiert werden soll. Natürlich ist die Differenz von „Geist“ und „Buchstabe“, von Sinn und Text, die spannungsgrundlage für das Metier des Interpreten überhaupt. Natürlich sind Werktreue und Texttreue zwei verschiedene Aspekte der Deutung, aber sie sind schwerlich im Sinne einer Entscheidung gegeneinander auszuspielen. [My translation] Hans-Joachim Hinrichsen, ‘Werk und Wille, Text und Treue: Über Freiheit und Grenzen der musikalischen Interpretation’, in *Werktreue: Was ist Werk, was Treue*, ed. Gerhard Brunner and Sarah Zalfen (Oldenburg: Böhlau, 2011), 35.

²⁷ Christensen, ‘Four-Hand Piano Transcription’, 268.

nineteenth century. Around 1800, the performance of music still counted as a kind of recitation [*Vortrag*].²⁸ This statement obscures a great deal more than it claims to illuminate. That performance acts were not *thought of* or *written about* as the results of deliberate hermeneutic or interpretative strategies does nothing to shrink the veritable mountain of evidence that eighteenth-century performers routinely “deviated” from the letter of the score in ways that were intentional and carefully judged, if not self-consciously exegetical: *ex tempore* embellishment, and improvisation more generally, formed an integral part of an eighteenth-century performer’s craft.²⁹ They did not think of these elements as interpretative per se, but it is beyond doubt that strategies we understand today as ‘interpretative’ or ‘interventionist’ were commonplace. When we turn our attention to Fischer, we face a similar quandary about the appropriateness of applying ahistorical labels: not everything we most readily identify as ‘transcriptions’ would have been identifiable as such to musicians of Fischer’s generation, who inhabited the musical culture that Liszt and Wagner had shaped. To understand Fischer’s recordings in a historical context, we must accept that interventions on the letter of the score in the service of sympathetic reimaginings would have constituted no less important a part of the *Vortrag* as actually playing the notes.

‘Transcription’ is therefore used in this article only insofar as it supplies an imperfect but widely understood label for a set of musical practices that are audible in Fischer’s recording. To a twenty-first-century listener, many of these will resemble

‘transcription’, but this resemblance is only invoked to illustrate how the performance and ‘transcription-like’ approaches are inseparable in Fischer’s Bach-pianism.

Approaches to Editions

Before encountering any of Fischer’s performances, it is necessary to demonstrate conclusively that these are not merely the result of ignorant adherence to an extreme romantic edition. Here, I turn to examples from the *Well-Tempered Clavier*, which in many ways are indicative of attitudes towards editing in the round.³⁰ Once again, we find tensions between what Fischer writes at different points in his life. Fischer emphasises his filiation with the tradition of Beethoven as transmitted through Czerny, Liszt, and d’Albert:

There was Beethoven, who influenced Czerny. Czerny passed on in his school of piano playing how Beethoven had played. He set down in print what remained in his memory of how Beethoven played the Bachian fugues in his edition of the *Well-Tempered Clavier*. Can we not accept with near certainty that Czerny entrusted his favoured pupil, Liszt, with everything he knew about Beethoven? And this very Liszt was the teacher of almost every great pianist of a generation ago. When we heard d’Albert play, then, we reaped the spiritual fruits of many giants – so stretches a long chain reaching to the beginnings of Art, and in this sense, ‘tradition’ is no empty word.³¹

²⁸ ‘Dass eine musikalische Aufführung als Interpretation bezeichnet oder auch nur empfunden wird, ist ein relativ junges Phänomen, das sich allmählich seit der Mitte des 19. Jahrhunderts durchgesetzt hat. Noch gegen 1800 wurde die Aufführung von Musik mit der Kategorie des Vortrags erfasst.’ [My translation] Hinrichsen, ‘Werk und Wille’, 26.

²⁹ See among others, Robert Levin, ‘Improvised Embellishments in Mozart’s Keyboard Music’, *Early Music* 20/2 (1992): 221–33; See also José Antonio Bowen ‘Performance Practice versus Performance Analysis: Why Should Performers Study Performance’, *Performance Practice Review* 9/1 (1996), 29–31.

³⁰ In this exercise, I am painfully aware of the gradations and nuance arising not only from expressive markings and dynamics, but also the particular quality of fingering and hand distribution; the organisation of pitches and durations, however, stands as a bellwether of these much more fleeting factors.

³¹ ‘Da war Beethoven, der Czerny beeinflusste; Czerny hat seine Schule des Pianofortespiels berichtet, wie Beethoven spielte, er hat seine Ausgabe der » Wohltemperierten Klaviers « von Bach niedergelegt, was ihm von Beethovens Vortrag der Bachschen Fugen in Erinnerung geblieben war – können wir da nicht fast mit Gewißheit annehmen, daß dieser Czerny seinem Lieblingsschüler Liszt alles, was er von Beethoven wußte, überlieferte? Und dieser Liszt war Lehrer von fast allen großen Pianisten der vorigen Generation. Wenn wir nun d’Albert hörten, da ernteten wir die geistigen Früchte vieler Großen – und so geht eine lange Kette zurück, bis in die Anfänge von Kunst, und Tradition ist in diesem Sinne kein leeres Wort.’ [My translation] Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 33–34.

See also a promotional film for the LP reissue of Fischer’s 78rpm records, containing remarks in French, filmed in Zürich as early as 1953 or as late as 1957 according to Roger Smithson. An edited version of the footage appears in the documentary film *The Art of the Piano: Great Pianists of the 20th Century* (NVC Arts, 2000), at 1h07m32s. Tantalisingly for the question of editions, the first page of Albert Lévêque’s edition of the *Well-Tempered Clavier* (Salabert no. 5458) appears briefly on screen in this segment. However, it was published only in 1948, long after the completion of Fischer’s recording.

One might expect Fisher to have used Czerny's edition, then. On the other hand, Fischer was a vocal proponent of a less interventionist editorial practice:

If only the original conception of the composer had reached us unadulterated – but then came publishers, who vied in the making of *editions*. A Beethoven, a Bach were littered with slurs, dots, fortes and pianos. One might still accept this if it were possible to recognize what came from Beethoven and what came from Mr. X. Much has been put right in recent times, and the efforts of Breitkopf, Peters, Steingräber, and others to reconstruct the original text cannot be commended enough.³²

Two of the publishing houses he acknowledges as praiseworthy in this quotation had philologically exacting editions of Bach's keyboard works in their catalogue. Breitkopf published the Bach Gesellschaft Ausgabe (henceforth, BGA), which appeared in instalments between 1851 and 1899. Steingräber published Hans Bischoff's complete edition of the keyboard works, which had gained widespread use among performers at the time of Fischer's musical education.

The Czerny tradition does appear to have played a role in shaping Fischer's view, but this role is limited, and the comparison of the 1933–37 recordings with earlier piano rolls demonstrates that his views were revised during his lifetime in favour of something resembling the scholarly consensus exemplified by Bischoff and Kroll. In Prelude and Fugue in C-sharp minor from Book I Fischer's approach bears witness (a) to a familiarity

with Czerny, and (b) to a revised view in older age, by the time he recorded the set electrically for His Master's Voice. In both documents, we hear the distribution of ties as they appear in the Czerny edition (Example 1a). On the piano roll, Fischer exhibits a tendency to alter melodic contour by raising the seventh of the scale, resulting in a sharper sense of harmonic direction. He seems to have preferred the natural seventh, as in Bischoff and Kroll, ten years later in the recording studio (Example 1b). The second example, bar 94 of the Fugue, is also puzzling.

Although the harmonic itch to raise the $b\sharp'$ is understandable, the sources giving this reading are few and far between and, like Example 2, it is not a variant reading he could have read in the critical reports of either Bischoff or Kroll.³³ That Fischer's use of ties remained characteristic of Czerny's edition is most distinct in the case of the Prelude in B-flat minor from Book I at bar 10 (Example 2). At bar 4, he makes the same unusual choice in 1923 and 1933: he ties the f' in the lowest voice (Example 2).

This reading is found only in Czerny. Because it seems to be comparatively rare or of questionable provenance,³⁴ it does not receive mention in the critical reports of Bischoff or Kroll. Fischer might, for stylistic reasons entirely his own, have preferred not to rearticulate the f' at the same time as the $g\flat'$. If he read it in any edition, it was Czerny's.

It is worth noting that Fischer's adherence to Czerny in his later recordings is limited to ties and onsets, but where Czerny constitutes a minority report on matters of pitch, Fischer's choices are broadly reflective of the scholarly editions. In

Roger Smithson, 'Chronological Discography', 28.

³² 'Wenn nun wenigstens dieses Urbild des Komponisten uns rein übermittelt würde – aber nun kamen die Verleger und Wetteiferten an Ausgaben. Ein Beethoven, Bach wurde übersät mit Bogen, Punkten, fortes und pianos, und man könnte sie noch gelten lassen, wenn erkenntlich wäre, was von Beethoven, was von Herrn X. stammt. Die neueste Zeit hat darin wieder viel gut gemacht. Und die Bemühungen von Breitkopf, Peters, Steingraeber und andern, den Originaltext wiederherzustellen, sind nicht genug zu begrüßen.' Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 26–27.

³³ The reading appears in Busoni's edition and in a small minority of manuscript sources, including Mus.Hs.210. It was revised in the 1840s according to Czerny, but the late nineteenth-century reprints of Czerny I have consulted do not contain this reading. It is not impossible that this variant emerged more or less accidentally as a result of nineteenth-century musicians finding the passage just "works better" with the chromatically tighter use of the leading note.

³⁴ It appears in P1075 (see note 28), P578 (copy by Johannes Ringk before or around 1740) and a late eighteenth century copy of uncertain provenance held at the Österreichische Nationalbibliothek as Mus.Hs.210 that was extensively revised in the mid-nineteenth century according to Czerny.

See Yo Tomita, 'The Sources of J. S. Bach's "Well-Tempered Clavier" II in Vienna, 1777-1801', *Bach* 29/2 (1998): 13–14.

A smudge on Altnickol's copy, P402, could potentially, given a poor enough photographic reproduction, be misread as a tie. The only widely available source printing this variant would have been Czerny and other derivative editions.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Example 1. Prelude and Fugue in C-sharp minor BWV 849 (Book I).

Example 1c, Fischer rearticulates the second minim of bar 102 in the Fugue in C-sharp minor from Book I. This choice was perhaps allowed to stand because it did not violate the scholarly consensus about what pitches needed to be sounded. It behoves us to notice that the decision-making process leading to that specific performance is highly unlikely to revolve around

the deliberate choice of Hoffmeister or Czerny as a source *qua* source, but rather must have stemmed from the presumed effectiveness of this reading. It is not far-fetched to suggest that for Fischer, this gave more contour, more clarity to the descending chromatic scale in minims that follows.

Example 2. Comparison of ties in the Prelude in B-flat minor BWV 867 (Book I) between Czerny and accepted text.

Several significant examples prevent one from accepting that the Czerny had a dominant role in shaping Fischer's Bach pianism. Some isolated readings (that also appeared first in Forkel's edition for Hoffmeister), may find themselves in Fischer's performances. But none of the most distinctive (some might say egregious) features of the Czerny edition appears to be reflected in Fischer's recorded performances. These include:

- Czerny's elaborate reworking of bars 16-18 in the Prelude in C-sharp minor, of unaccountable provenance.³⁵
- The insertion of the so-called Schwencke bar.³⁶

- The addition of an extraneous bass note at the end of the Prelude in B-flat major, Book 1. A devotee of Czerny's edition, or even a musician so steeped in that tradition as to have unthinkingly followed Czerny's editorial choices, would be expected to render something resembling this passage.

Moreover, the suggestion that Fischer shows, in places, a preference for Forkel's readings, many of which find themselves in Czerny's edition, is not convincing either. Fischer differs from Forkel and Czerny, for example, in the Prelude in E minor from Book I. He plays the ornamented version of the Prelude, as in the *post correcturam* autograph.³⁷

³⁵

³⁶ Several nineteenth-century editions insert a bar in the Prelude in C major of Book I between bars 22 and 23. The insertion softens a supposedly abrupt progression and is credited to Johann Friedrich Gottlieb Schwencke, whose copies of the prelude were the first to include it. Schwencke claimed to have copied it from now untraceable copies of the autograph. Czerny includes this bar in his edition, but both Kroll and Bischoff, along with most editors in the later nineteenth century, reject it.

³⁷ There are effectively two versions of the movement, one with more elaborate ornamentation, thought by Forkel to have been a youthful sin that Bach later replaced with a simpler, soberer melodic contour. The opposite of this hypothesis has since been confirmed by empirical means. The simple version appeared in Forkel's 1801 edition, then successive printings of Czerny's edition. Fischer performs the elaborately ornamented version as it appears in Kroll in the main text and in Bischoff as an *ossia*.

See Johann Nikolaus Forkel, *Johann Sebastian Bach: His Life, Art, and Work* (London: Constable & Co., [1802] 1920), 145.

There is a similar choice to be made at bar 41 of the Fugue in F major that immediately follows it, where Fischer performs the simple version instead, favouring Forkel over the autograph. This indicates a case-by-case adjudication of the options according to need.

In the second book of the *Well-Tempered Clavier*, the pitches in Fischer's 1930s recordings share with Bischoff a tendency to prefer the Altnickol readings where these differ from those of Kimberger and other competing traditions.³⁸

Though some aspects of the Czerny tradition influenced Fischer, the evidence from the *Well-Tempered Clavier* shows that by the 1930s, during the zenith of his recording career, his performances were primarily informed by the scholarly consensus about Bach's text exemplified by Kroll (BGA) and Bischoff. Fischer's adherence to the wealth of expressive markings in Czerny is, in general terms, not close enough to suggest that this was a predominating influence, or a key motivation for the performance approaches scrutinised below. At any rate, the choice of pitches in his performances conforms to no single edition. Fischer thus seems to take an approach that might be described as informed eclecticism. Most importantly, this attitude of informed eclecticism, particularly as regards the complex editorial questions in the second book of the *Well-Tempered Clavier*, could only have been possible by consulting a scholarly edition and comparing extant variants. Finally, this eclecticism shows how, even upstream of the hermeneutically empowered transcription-like approaches to performance, we find an analogous approach to conceiving of the text.

From Score to Transcription

Playing Bach on the piano accords with Fischer's philosophically idealist conception of works as both real and at the same time, inaccessible. According to these assumptions, the elusive spirit

of the work does not necessarily reside in the specific sounds of Bach's time, but in their organising principles: 'among Bach's keyboard works, I find pieces for organ, for violin, voice, orchestra, for spinet – indeed, for an instrument which does not exist: an instrument, which, like the algebraic formula, would express "music in itself." *The most concentrated essence of musically logical thought.*'³⁹ Clearly to Fischer, playing the harpsichord placed limitations on the work, just as playing it on a modern piano would, *in different ways*. Fischer celebrated the piano's versatility because it responded so well to his aim of conveying this 'concentrated essence of musical thought' as a general effect rather than as historical truth. We also see in this quotation the implication of various dichotomies of form and content (Bach's music has a content that is too complex and too perfect to capture totally in a performance, which, in turn, has a fundamentally different ontological status), structure and decoration, surface and depth, appearance and existence – and of course that familiar bugbear: work and performance. What is thought-provoking about the confrontation of Fischer's statements and Fischer's recorded performances is the way that the acceptance of this network of dichotomies (onto which value-laden hierarchies inevitably graft themselves) produced highly creative, spontaneous performances.

Fischer does not make any specific prescription about how these effects are to be rendered in performance, but he undoubtedly considers the sonic *character* of the harpsichord, engaging "at arm's length" with the sound-world of the eighteenth century. In his 1943 essay *Johann Sebastian Bach*, he calls attention to the transcribed nature of the keyboard works themselves: 'the task of the musician is to discern the intrinsic character of the composition, to distinguish harpsichord works from organ pieces, delicate clavichord poetry from imposing masterworks imitating the concerto grosso'.⁴⁰ Fischer's writings bear

³⁸ Examples include: bottom voice, beat 1, bar 50, Prelude in E major BWV 878; top voice, beat 1, bar 53, Fugue in F minor BWV 881; bottom voice, beat 2, bar 6, Prelude in G-sharp minor BWV 887; alto voice, beats 1–2, bar 41, Fugue in B-flat minor BWV 891. Out of these four examples, three – all except the G-sharp minor prelude – also contradict Czerny. Moreover, Fischer follows BGA and Bischoff over Czerny in: alto voice, beat 1, bar 15, Fugue in C-sharp minor BWV 873; several key moments in the Prelude in F-sharp minor BWV 883 (most prominently, top voice, beat 3, b. 33 – the preparation of the Neapolitan harmony); top voice, beat 2, bar 24, Prelude in B minor BWV 893.

³⁹ 'Unter Bachs Klavierwerken finde ich solche für Orgel, für Geige, Gesang, Orchester, für Spinett, ja für ein Instrument, das es nicht gibt: ein Instrument, das der algebraischen Formel gleich »Musik an sich« ausdrücken würde. Konzentriertester Extrakt musikalisch logischen Denkens.' [My translation; my italics] Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 62.

⁴⁰ 'Aufgabe des Musikers ist es, den Komposition innewohnenden Charakter herauszufinden, Cembalowerke von Orgelstücken, zarte Clavichordpoesien von rauschenden, Concerto Grosso imitierenden Prachstücken zu unterscheiden.' [My translation] Fischer, *Bach*, 32.

important resemblances to Busoni's. In his *Sketch of a New Aesthetic of Music*, Busoni prefigures Fischer's remarks about Bach keyboard works:

Every notation is, in itself, the transcription of an abstract idea. The instant the pen seizes it, the idea loses its original form... The performance of a work is also a transcription, and still, whatever liberties it may take, it can never annihilate the original. The musical art-work exists, before its tones resound and after they die away, *complete and intact*. It exists both within and outside time.⁴¹

Moreover, he adds that 'Beethoven's piano compositions sound like transcriptions of orchestral works; most of Schumann's orchestral compositions like arrangements from pieces for the piano – and they are so in a way.'⁴² From here to Fischer's characterisation of Bach's keyboard works as a compendium of eighteenth-century musical soundscapes, there is only a stone's throw. Indeed, Fischer uses very similar wording at a few decades' distance.⁴³

Even if the younger pianist arrived at different performances, the central argument of Busoni about performance and works seems to have had a defining influence on Fischer. Both the vast and varied affordances of the modern piano and the mental processes of transcription could have offered Fischer possibilities for solving some of the problems related to finding the spirit inside the work: thinking of Bach performance on modern

instruments as mediated by the process of transcription establishes a musical division of labour in which respect can be given to the composer's presumed ideas (as intuited in the text through exegesis, taste, and personality) and through which the performer may exercise a degree of creativity. For Busoni and potentially for Fischer, the features of the music written in score provide the blueprint for hermeneutic conclusions; these antecedents perhaps explain how for Fischer, a scrupulous attitude to editing did not preclude a free attitude towards performance.

What is even more interesting is how Fischer, at the end of his life, tangentially described a listening experience that may be familiar, in phenomenological terms, to a present-day music lover – that of listening with one's mind for something that is *beyond* what is actually sounded out:

Nature knows and loves darkness, and the more the spiritual world – indeed the world in general – is 'discovered' and 'described', the less novelty occurs. Already one begins to understand that the charm emanating from the sparse sound of the harpsichord, its purported 'chastity', the charm of Bach's compositions for solo violin or cello, resides in that the hearer is compelled to flex his imagination and mentally reinstate what is missing.⁴⁴

This is the justification I find for writing of 'mental processes' when discussing the audible phenomena

⁴¹ Ferruccio Busoni, *Sketch of a New Aesthetic of Music*, trans. Th. Baker (New York: G. Schirmer, 1911), 17–18. [Italics in the translation. Orig: 'Jede Notation ist schon Transkription eines abstrakten Einfalls. Mit den Augenblick, da die Feder sich seiner bemächtigt, verliert der Gedanke seine Originalgestalt... Auch der Vortrag eines Werkes ist eine Transkription, und auch dieser kann – er mag noch so frei sich gebärden – niemals das Original aus der Welt schaffen. Denn das musikalische Kunstwerk steht, vor seinem Er tönen und nachdem es vorübergeklungen, ganz unversehrt da. Es ist zugleich in und außer der Zeit, und sein Wesen ist es, das uns eine greifbare Vorstellung des sonst ungreifbar Begriffes von den Idealität der Zeit geben kann.' Ferruccio Busoni, *Entwurf einer neuen Ästhetik der Tonkunst* (Leipzig: Insel-Verlag, 1907), 22–23.]

⁴² Busoni, *Sketch of a New Aesthetic*, 18–19. [Orig: 'Im übrigen muten die meisten Klavierkompositionen Beethovens wie Transkriptionen vom Orchester an, die meisten Schumannschen Orchesterwerken wie Übertragungen vom Klavier – und sinds in gewisser Weise auch.' Busoni, *Entwurf einer neuen Ästhetik*, 23.]

⁴³ With writing comes already a form of transcription. There are certainly musical ideas that are intended immediately for a specific instrument, for example, a voice. Indeed, the thought of an instrument's sound can be the direct cause of a musical idea – but in general, the composer marshals the pure music of his inspiration into a more or less adequate, suitable instrument. He often must do violence to his imagination; the possibilities and the limits of an instrument confine him. [My translation: 'Bei dieser Niederschrift erfolgt schon ein Art von Transkription. Gewiß gibt es musikalische Ideen, die sofort für ein bestimmtes Instrument, zum Beispiel eine Stimme, gedacht sind, ja, die Vorstellung des Klanges eines Instrumentes kann direkt die Ursache eines musikalischen Einfalls sein – aber in ganzen rieht der Komponist doch die reine Musik seiner Einbildungskraft für ein mehr oder weniger zureichendes, geeignetes Instrument ein. Er muß dabei oft seiner Phantasie Gewalt antun, die Möglichkeiten, die Grenzen eines Instrumentes beschränken ihn?'] Fischer, *Betrachtungen*, 25.

⁴⁴ 'Die Natur kennt und liebt das Dunkel, und je mehr die seelische, ja überhaupt die Welt 'entdeckt und 'beschrieben' ist, um so weniger geschieht Neues. Schon fängt man an zu erkennen, dass der Reiz des dürftigen Cembaloklanges, seine sogenannten 'Keuschheit, der Reiz der Kompositionen Bachs für Solovioline und Cello darin liegt, dass der Hörer gezwungen wird, das Fehlende selbst zu ersetzen, seine imaginationskraft anzuspinnen.' Fischer, *Aufgaben*, 29.

of Fischer's recorded performances, seeing how it calls upon a certain number of tasks in the mind of the listener as well as that of the player.

Overcoming Limitations

Let us begin with an example that is innocuous enough. Anyone who plays the *Well-Tempered Clavier* will at least have felt the temptation to do the following, and, as soon as one listens for it, one finds that this liberty with the score is in more widespread use than one expects. Example 3 shows a three-way comparison between the text as Fischer would likely have received it (as edited by Kroll and Bischoff, who do not, in this case, differ significantly) and notated transcriptions of two performances – one on a Welte-Mignon piano roll of 1923, and the other on his 1933 recording for His Master's Voice. In this example, there are indeed a few moments of enlarged sonority with octaves – a familiar set of procedures redolent of the tradition of romantic transcription – as well as certain other subtle doublings. What is more telling, however, is the way in which Fischer makes a habit of rearticulating long notes.

The techniques on display here make explicit a thought-process that most often remains tacit. Fischer's performance approach requires him to have attended to the generic and/or idiomatic association between the fugue's notation and the archaic *Ricercar*. In stylistic and generic terms, the notation alludes to the affordances of the organ and implicitly sets these in tension with the real affordances of the piano. This passage is challenging because of the comparatively rapid decay of the sounds produced on a piano (or, for that matter, on a harpsichord or clavichord), relative to their full notated value on the page. Fischer responded to this challenge by

rearticulating long note-values, as shown in Example 3. Crucially, Fischer's plan appears to have changed in significant ways between 1923 and 1933, lending credence to the idea that this was an *ad hoc* "working-out" rather than a permanent rewriting.

At the dominant pedal-point beginning in bar 105, Fischer sustains the tone of the bass note with asynchronous rearticulations in the 1923 piano roll, so that the metrical accents in the other voices are matched by sonority from the bass voice on the downbeats of bars 106 and 107. The urge to "refresh" the bass note in moments when the other voices have metrical accents is also on display on the downbeat of bar 111. It is also relevant to note that the bass is not the only voice to receive this treatment: the four tied semibreves in the uppermost voice in bars 112–15 are broken up in both performances. In fact the longest note-value left unbroken is the bass part in the 1933 recording at bars 111–13, lasting eight crotchet beats and one quaver.

This example does not only show crafty solutions to an abstruse problem. It exemplifies a small but important space that Fischer has pried open through his choice of performance strategy between the notation and its performance.

This is a practical demonstration both of the difference, and of the phenomenal points of contact between the ideal archetype encoded in the notation – the various pedal points held for the value of *lunga* – and the imperfect, earthly performance that alludes obliquely to this elusive archetype.

c. 1923 Piano roll

99

1933 recording

Text as in BGA/Bischoff

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Example 3 (1 of 2). Prelude and Fugue in C-sharp minor BWV 849 (Book I), Fugue.⁴⁵

⁴⁵ Red arrows highlight occasions where Fischer does not observe a tie, or breaks up a long note value with a new onset.

* Bischoff identifies an alternative reading for this bar, with a minim *c*[#] in the uppermost voice in the second half of bar 102, as originating in Forkel's 1801 edition. Interestingly, this reading appears in Czerny, but not in Busoni.

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The image shows three systems of musical notation for a piano piece. Each system has a treble staff and a bass staff. Red arrows point to specific notes in the bass line, indicating doubling or performance choices. The music is in C-sharp minor, BWV 849, Fugue.

Example 3 (2 of 2). Prelude and Fugue in C-sharp minor BWV 849 (Book I), Fugue.

Fischer could conjure into existence something *like* the archetype, as he would have seen it, only by modifying in the letter of the text. What is important to bear in mind is that Fischer was a representative of what could easily be classified as conservatism. After all, he did not advocate explicitly or especially forcefully for the performer's freedom to intervene. His commitment to the work concept is made abundantly clear in his writing, editing, and pedagogical advice. What is therefore astonishing is the level of freedom and individuality that are practised *within* and, I would argue, *as a direct consequence* of this artistic ideology, viewing the work as something tantalisingly out of reach, and performances as imperfect, temporary attempts to grasp it.

Conjuring Sound-Worlds

The most distinctive feature of Fischer's playing today would likely be the frequent doubling of voices in octaves and thickening of chords. A comprehensive catalogue of octave doublings in Fischer's discography would occupy much time and space. In most cases, a climactic entry of a fugue subject, an important cadence, or an extended pedal point are highlighted as a result. But in the coming section I would like to explore the mindset that permits these uses. And two

significant cases in Fischer's discography illustrate this.

In the Fantasia and A minor BWV 904 and the Prelude in B minor BWV 869, the use of the procedure is in both cases integrated into the fabric of the performance and, arguably into the fabric of the piece that these performances conjure into existence. Fischer's performance of the Prelude in B minor BWV 869 diverges significantly from what is written in the text: this is at least the assessment that would meet a performer attempting the same performance in the twenty-first century. The near entirety of the bass line is doubled, as shown in Example 4.

Fischer plays this bass line with an articulation that is characteristic of moving bass lines on an organ's pedal board. Each note is weighty and detached, although not overpowering in this generally quiet movement, suggesting a modest choice of registration.

Fischer's performance moves closer to what would be called today a transcription of the work rather than the mere realisation of a score that would be expected from the verb 'perform'. Still, Fischer, along with countless Bach enthusiasts in the 1930s, would have understood and heard this recording

exclusively as a performance of Bach's prelude. An explanation of Fischer's decision-making would seek to understand how the three-voice texture of the prelude as writ evokes the trio ensemble. Fischer was doubtless familiar with Bach's Organ Trios, the 'three-voice arrangement (usually of a chamber trio) for two manuals and pedal' particularly cherished by Bach and his circle.⁴⁶ Other generic allusions latently audible in the Prelude – again through the offsetting of two lyrical upper voices with a walking bass – might have been the Chorale-Prelude 'Nun Komm der Heiden Heiland' BWV 659 or the orchestral ritornello in the Duet 'So ist mein Jesus nun gefangen' in the *Matthew Passion* BWV 244. Fischer implies a slight change in registration with the use of single notes in the bass from bar 19. The middle section of the Prelude is given a quieter treatment and allows Fischer another significant sonic contrast with the return of the doubled octaves in the bass voice at bar 36.

Fischer's performance gestures towards something *beyond* the notation because it is manifestly fashioned out of allusions to something these textures have in common in terms of their underlying, inaccessible existence. In this case, we are invited to hear organ registration or orchestration instead of harpsichord or even piano music. Fischer knew how Bach used and transformed the stylistic features of the trio sonata in a wide variety of settings and moods. This may have led Fischer to the transformative rendering of the B minor Prelude that we hear in the recording. Such a course of action was to humbly continue in Bach's footsteps: by interpreting the trio-like musical features in this particular way, with the bass as though it were being played on the organ's pedalboard, or by a massed bank of orchestral strings, Fischer was presenting a facet of the works, which he had discerned on the basis of his sense of the work's inner spirit. A similar porousness between transcription and 'rendition' is to be heard in Fischer's 1937 recording of the Fantasia in A minor BWV 904, which seems completely transformed in Fischer's performance. But this sense of complete transformation is – in part – illusive. Fischer only makes changes to the four statements of the chordal 'refrain' (bb.1-12, 31-43, 69-80, 100-111), leaving the contrapuntal sections between them entirely untouched.

The illusion of cohesion is so strong due to Fischer's choice of passages to enlarge. In the text, each of these chordal refrains gives a strong sense of formal and tonal closure, functioning as waypoints in the running quaver counterpoint of the 'interludes'. In this sense, Fischer is merely amplifying what is already audible in the compositional features of the movement. As always, the choice of doublings appears to serve a conceptual purpose. Fischer's enlarged rendition uses the bass octaves to separate sonically the two lower voices and reinforces the antiphony between the two in bars 6–10. One also notices that this same separation in register allows Fischer to separate the middle voice from the others in the opening bars.

It should be noted that Fischer also makes strong contrasts in his treatment of the three refrains. The first (Example 5) employs a time-honoured pianistic technique of enlarging chords and giving bass lines emphasis with doubled octaves, but the second, as seen in Example 6, doubles the two upper lines and is performed quietly. In this case, contrast is achieved by changes of volume and timbre in both directions. The resulting impression of contrapuntal texture is also completely changed by this alternative approach. Here the two upper lines are blended seamlessly into a dense texture but remain perceptually bright because of the register on the piano in which they are played. Why specifically the Fantasia and Fugue in A minor?

⁴⁶ Stinson, Preface to *The Keyboard Transcriptions from the Bach Circle*, ed. Russell Stinson (Madison, WI: A-R Editions, 1992), vii.

Blurred Boundaries

Andante

Example 4 (1 of 2). Notated transcription of Fischer's Performance of the Prelude in B minor BWV 869 (Book I).⁴⁷

⁴⁷ N.B. Fischer does not observe the repeat at b. 17, plausibly to accommodate the whole Prelude and Fugue on two sides (the change of side is at b. 24 of the Fugue). I have notated the ornament in b. 17 as in Fischer's performance. The right hand at 17 reads as follows in BGA & Bischoff:

The L.H. trill at b. 16 is played in the bottom octave.

Example 4 (2 of 2). Notated transcription of Fischer's Performance of the Prelude in B minor BWV 869 (Book I).

One reason that makes this example especially compelling is that there is no extant tradition of which the author is aware, of annotated editions that would have exerted influence on its performance and reception to the same degree as Hans von Bülow's edition did for the *Chromatic Fantasia and Fugue*.

Several performers in later recordings give the Fantasia a treatment that is, in its essence, very close to Fischer's, i.e. using pianistic means to amplify the structural contrast between the refrains and interludes.⁴⁸

There remains a thought-provoking uncertainty, still, as to how this approach continued to be viewed as almost routine in the case of BWV 904, while a performance of BWV 869, with the application of the same criteria, would be unthinkable without the application of a fig-leaf caveat in the concert programme or track listing.

⁴⁸ The history of this particular set of procedures continues into the present, including Alfred Brendel in 1976 and, most recently, Víkingur Ólafsson in 2018. There are unquestionably similarities also with Samuil Feinberg in 1961. While this could be a separate investigation unto itself, we appear to see here a predominantly unwritten tradition and transmission.

Blurred Boundaries

1937 Recording

The first system of the musical score, labeled '1937 Recording', consists of two staves. The upper staff is in treble clef and contains a complex texture of overlapping chords and melodic fragments. The lower staff is in bass clef and features a more rhythmic, eighth-note pattern. The music is in A minor and 3/4 time. The system concludes with a double bar line and a fermata over the final chord.

Text after BGA/Bischoff

The second system, labeled 'Text after BGA/Bischoff', shows a revised version of the first system. The upper staff has been simplified, focusing on the main melodic line with fewer overlapping notes. The lower staff remains largely the same as in the 1937 recording, providing a clear harmonic and rhythmic foundation.

The second system of the musical score, starting at measure 5, consists of two staves. The upper staff continues the melodic development with various intervals and rests. The lower staff provides a steady accompaniment with eighth-note patterns and chordal support.

The third system of the musical score, starting at measure 7, consists of two staves. The upper staff features a more active melodic line with frequent sixteenth-note runs. The lower staff continues its accompaniment role with consistent rhythmic patterns.

The fourth system of the musical score, starting at measure 9, consists of two staves. The upper staff shows a continuation of the melodic motifs, with some chromatic movement. The lower staff maintains the accompaniment, with some changes in chordal texture.

The fifth system of the musical score, starting at measure 11, consists of two staves. The upper staff concludes the melodic phrase with a final cadence. The lower staff provides a clear harmonic resolution.

Example 5. Fantasia and Fugue in A minor, BWV 904, Fantasia.

1937 Recording

Text after BGA/Bischoff

Example 6. Fantasia in and Fugue in A minor BWV 904, Fantasia.

From Transcription to Score

Even more interesting, and perhaps unjustifiably overlooked, are Fischer's performances of Bach transcriptions. These are certainly fewer in number in his catalogue. The outstanding example is without doubt his recording of Busoni's piano transcription of Bach's Prelude and Fugue in E-flat major for organ BWV 552, made in April 1933 on four sides of 78rpm records. Pianists today embarking on the performance of Bach-Busoni sometimes, deliberately or not, reason that these transcriptions are successful in their own way – as worthwhile, thought-provoking nineteenth-century musical artefacts – even if, as Bach, or as attempts to “portray” century music, they seem disconcertingly wrong. To ventriloquise this train of thought, ‘we hear an awful not more Busoni than Bach here, but we continue playing them because Busoni is worth listening to.’ Fischer's Bach-Busoni is surprisingly, devotedly Bachian – in its own way. Fischer makes several carefully chosen but significant departures from the letter of Busoni's text, changes that can only have resulted from a close familiarity with the original organ score.⁴⁹ These changes suggest that, just as Fischer was listening *through* Bach's notation for something beyond it, he was doing the same thing with Busoni's notation.

Fischer's fingerprints are undoubtedly on the pianistic layout we hear in his recording at crucial junctures in the Fugue. Example 7 shows how, in bars 27–30, Busoni has rearranged the upper voices, possibly to maintain the tenor and bass voices as writ while adding sonority in the treble register. In his recording, Fischer reinstates the layering of the upper two voices found in the organ version. Fischer doubles both upper voices more or less systematically until b. 29, a similar procedure as the one seen in Example 6

Another noteworthy feature in Example 7 is how Busoni, who expressed an aversion for arpeggiating chords if they are too widely spread to comfortably perform,⁵⁰ disrupted the flow of crotchets in the upper voices to accommodate the middle line in bb. 31–32. Fischer accepts the compromise of a non-simultaneous attack and maintains the characteristic flow of crotchets from the organ version, resorting to a familiar technique of the *Partiturspieler*, who will readily dart around on the piano, covering different layers with non-synchronous attacks.

⁴⁹ The following demonstration touches on the choices of pitch, which are the most quantifiable variable, but it should be said, that the analysis presented below is meant to stand in for a comprehensive performance approach encompassing contrapuntal phrasing, shaping of dynamics and section-level pacing.

⁵⁰ On the first page of the Prelude, Busoni warns the performer that ‘it is essential for the chords, no matter how widely spaced, to be played with all notes sounding simultaneously – that is, without arpeggiation.’

Ferruccio Busoni, *Tocatta and Fugue in D minor and the Other Bach Transcriptions* (Mineola, N.Y.: Dover Publications, 1996), 15.

Bach-Busoni-Fischer

Bach-Busoni

poco marc. e cresc.

piti cresc.

mf marc.

Bach

Example 7. Prelude and Fugue in E-flat major BWV 552, Fugue. Comparison between a notated transcription of Fischer's Performance, Busoni's Transcription, and Bach original (after BGA 3). N.B. Grey arpeggiation marks denote slightly non-simultaneous attacks in Fischer's performance.

Bach-Busoni-Fischer

The image displays a musical score for a fugue in E-flat major, BWV 552, comparing three different transcriptions: the original by J.S. Bach, a transcription by Ferruccio Busoni, and a performance by Heinrich Fischer. The score is presented in three systems, each with three staves. The top staff in each system is labeled 'Bach-Busoni-Fischer' and contains the notation for the three versions. The middle staff is labeled 'Bach' and the bottom staff is labeled 'Busoni'. The notation includes various musical symbols such as notes, rests, slurs, and dynamic markings like *ff* and *mf*. A measure number '111' is indicated at the beginning of the first system. The score illustrates differences in articulation, dynamics, and phrasing between the original and the two transcriptions.

Example 9. Prelude and Fugue in E-flat major BWV 552, Fugue. Comparison between a notated transcription of Fischer's Performance, Busoni's Transcription, and Bach original (after BGA 3)

with Bach's text for organ that he was reading Bach's notation *through* Busoni's notation, and indeed, reading something else through Bach's notation that is beyond even it. By performing the interstices between these two notated texts as they almost come into contact with one another, but do not perfectly converge, it is not unreasonable to suggest that, according to Fischer's understanding of musical works and musical performance, he was reading 'Bach's Music Itself' *through* these various written artefacts.

It is revealing that, both in the 'original' keyboard works and in Busoni's transcription, Fischer appears to be reading through the notation for something else that he uncovers as a result of deeply personal hermeneutic acts, effectively performing in the gap between transcription and performance. In light of these examples, we perhaps need not accept these as distinct and separately constituted fields of action. The categories of transcription and original are fraught at best.

Leech-Wilkinson observes that the issue of 'how to label a performance that may start from a classical score but result in a musical event that is quite unlike a typical performance is it ... can be a practical rather than a philosophical question (unless you're an analytical philosopher).'⁵³

He has also stated⁵⁴ that the term 'transcription' has too often been used as a fig-leaf to placate anxieties about supposedly corrupt or too interventionist performances – a semantic sleight of hand to demote a given musical activity to second-class status, as someone else's derivative creative work, having only an arm's-length relationship to the composer's 'original'.

More importantly, this use of 'transcription' has the all-too-convenient effect of maintaining the fiction that 'straight' performances render the text (and therefore the music) in a straightforward manner that somehow doesn't quite involve the creative agency of a performer. Walking in Fischer's shoes, there is another observation worth making. Somehow, being a transcriber involves more

responsibility than being a performer. In a very concrete sense, transcribers such as Liszt or Busoni produced *things* that would be engraved, printed, transported and sold, which made them more responsible than the giver of one performance on one occasion. Some kind of final product had to be decided upon, and its creator would have limited opportunities to change it subsequently. In this narrow sense, the Bach transcriptions of Liszt and Busoni have something like a fixed 'work-adjacent' ontological status. At any rate, the creator of a transcription seems to have a number of prerogatives and responsibilities: the chief among these is the expectation that the transcriber engage hermeneutically with the score at their disposal, attend to it closely enough that they can divine some kind of meaning from it that they can present in a personal, distinctive manner, in broad terms the expectation of having something to say and the willingness to risk reaching an unconvincing conclusion. Then again, Fischer also gave a permanent form to his performances in a way that involved significant investment of material resources and participation in commercial networks of dissemination and trade.

However, Fischer seems to have taken on many of these awkward responsibilities that a 'straight' model of performance risks neglecting – or at least does not always acknowledge explicitly. More than that, Fischer's example is a practical demonstration of one way (among many) to navigate obligations to the work while retaining healthy scepticism towards texts.

The gap between work and text is most pronounced in Fischer's recordings of Bach, Handel, and Mozart. The field of action afforded by the less detailed prescriptions of scores before the 1790s are merely examples in which the approach I have explored is most readily observed. But this practice of "reading through" texts for something else could doubtless have been undertaken more discretely in Fischer's recordings of Beethoven, Schubert, Schumann, and Brahms, for which he also gained significant critical acclaim.

⁵³ Daniel Leech-Wilkinson, 'Challenging Performance', §6.11, accessed 2 April 2023, <https://challengingperformance.com/the-book-6-11/>.

⁵⁴ Daniel Leech-Wilkinson, Round-table discussion, 'Rethinking Musical Transcription and Arrangement' conference, Cambridge, 18 May 2018.

Something about Fischer's Bach pianism seems, at nearly a century's remove, both surprisingly old-fashioned and surprisingly modern. Concerns that would be championed in the very different postwar environment by Theodore Adorno and other members of the Frankfurt School allude clearly to the kind of performance and the kind of 'knowledge through process' of which Fischer was an archetypal example:

As long as music requires any kind of interpretation whatsoever, its form defines itself through the tension between the composition's essence and its sensuous appearance... Devotion to the text means the constant effort to grasp that which it hides... an interpretation which does not bother about the music's meaning on the assumption that it will reveal itself of its own accord will inevitably be false if it fails to see that the meaning is always constituting itself anew.⁵⁵

Adorno, in 'Bach defended against his devotees', was reacting to the 'modernist' assumptions about musical performance that began to hold particular sway in the post-war era – the ideological commitment to letting the music speak for itself, abiding by the letter of the text, and generally the idea that only what is compulsory is permitted. Hill theorised that the shift towards a more self-effacing concept of performance was due to performers being 'conditioned by musicologists and critics to aspire to ideally objective readings of musical texts'.⁵⁶ Cook described as a 'telepathic fantasy' the twentieth-century understanding of

written notation as the pure product of the composer's mind, which performances could at best emulate imperfectly, or at worst corrupt.⁵⁷ This collection of views and practices has justifiably come under fire from many directions, and the idea of characterising performance as a form of imperfect striving towards a perfect, timeless archetype has consequently become profoundly unfashionable. Nowhere in Fischer's writings or transcribed addresses do we find anything approaching the deliberately anthropological reflections on display in Christopher Small or Cook about the social dimension of music-making or the production of meaning arising from social relationships. Similarly, there is nothing of the historical scepticism of a Taruskin or of the polemical advocacy for the performer's creative prerogatives of a Leech-Wilkinson. The musical ideology on display in Fischer's writings is, by any present-day estimation, almost reactionary: his belief in the existence and importance of musical masterworks amounts to an artistic credo, his sense of the performer's responsibilities to the composer a vow of obedience. But Fischer shows us how this particular ideology of musical performance need not cast the performer either in the role of a servile amanuensis or that of a corrupting deviant. His recordings and writings, considered side by side, show how the practice of listening for *something beyond* the notation frees the performer to act personally, creatively, and – in their own way – faithfully.

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⁵⁵ Theodor Adorno, *Prisms*, trans. Samuel and Shierry Weber (Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, 1982), 144.

⁵⁶ Robert Hill, '“Overcoming Romanticism”: On the Modernization of Twentieth-Century Performance Practice'. In *Music and Performance during the Weimar Republic*, ed. Brian Gilliam (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1994), 43–44.

⁵⁷ Nicholas Cook, *Beyond the Score: Music as Performance* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), 17.

Conference Reports

Medieval and Renaissance Music Conference 2023. Munich, 24-28 August 2023.

2023 marks 500 years since the founding of the court chapel of the dukes of Bavaria. The chapel quickly became associated with the highest standards of music-making, attracting talented musicians, foremost among them that 'Prince of Musicians' in the sixteenth century, Orlando di Lasso. With such musical pedigree, the Munich Residenz was a particularly fitting place for this year's Medieval and Renaissance Music Conference (MedRen). Over 300 papers across five parallel sessions and more than 30 submissions to the poster session made this one of the largest MedRen conferences ever—and a true return to normality after the disruptions of the pandemic.

As ever, the scholarship presented at MedRen ranged very widely. Musical works and practices from before 1000 CE to the seventeenth century and beyond were explored, perhaps with a little more on offer for those interested in the Renaissance than in the Middle Ages. All tastes were catered for: cultural history, source study, music theory, music analysis, and sound studies were all represented. This year's MedRen also continued the trend of recent iterations of the conference by expanding the geographic areas under consideration. While there were plenty of papers about France, German- and Italian-speaking lands, and Latin Christendom, there was also a greater sense of a global history of music under construction. Papers on Arabic and Jewish music theory and musical cultures offered fascinating comparisons with the music of the Christian West, while other papers analysed cases of cultural transfer or hybridity, in the movement of musical sources from East to West during the Crusades, for example, or a Latin song that made it as far as the Golden Horde. Broad questions of historiography and disciplinary changes were also broached. What can we learn from absence in sources of early music? Why do our histories of early music give short shrift to unwritten and improvisatory practices? How can we bring

modern theories of cognition and perception to bear on early music? And what are the potential applications of digital methods to the repertoires we perform and study?

Performance was, of course, never far away at MedRen. Delegates were treated to three wonderful concerts. Per-sonat performed a selection of fifteenth-century songs by Oswald von Wolkenstein and his central and western European contemporaries. Ensemble Phoenix offered a program of Spanish court music from the seventeenth century. And Ensemble Singer Pur sang sacred and secular works of the sixteenth century, including pieces by two musicians of the Munich court, Orlando di Lasso and Ludwig Senfl. Conference papers were themselves often accompanied by live performances. Danil Riabchikov illustrated his paper on caesurae in troubadour song with a recording from his group, Ensemble Labyrinthus, and lecture-recitals were given by Matthew Gouldstone and Avery Gosfield. It is always exciting to hear performances of musical works that have not been heard for hundreds of years. Fabrice Fitch presented the next installment of his reconstruction of Obrecht's *Missa Scaramella*, while Michael Winter partially reconstructed a didactic work from a newly discovered fragment that was copied in Tudor England. A team of musicians and scholars performed excerpts from the collection of German and Polish polyphonic dances known as Hess 1555, for which one of the partbooks is lost; works performed at this workshop will eventually be part of a complete reconstruction of this rich source.

There are many things that make MedRen special. It is the annual focus for early music research, and delegates come back year after year. Subsequently, there is a greater sense of community than at some of the larger general music conferences. MedRen is also a very welcoming conference: the whole academic community is represented, from graduate students right up to the most senior and distinguished scholars. Everyone is given a fair hearing and senior scholars are supportive of their

junior colleagues. But MedRen is also unique in its mix of delegates, who may be academics, performers, or both. Speaking primarily as a scholar who dabbles in performance, I have found the conversations between performers and scholars at MedRen to be stimulating and exciting. Discussing my own work with performers who know a repertory intimately has been inspirational and has pointed me in new directions that I would not otherwise have considered. I hope that performers who have attended MedRen have benefitted in kind from conversations with academics. All this is to say: if you are a performer of early music with something to say, do submit an abstract for MedRen. And if you are someone with an interest in early music history and performance, do consider coming along to the conference: the next meetings in Granada (2024), Newcastle and Durham (2025) and Warsaw (2026) promise delights both intellectual and musical.

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20th Biennial International Conference on Baroque Music. Haute École de Musique de Genève, 28 June – 2 July 2023.

Music scholars around the world congregated at Haute École de Musique de Genève from 28 July to 2 August 2023 for the 20th Biennial International Conference on Baroque Music, the first in-person meeting since the COVID-19 pandemic. Invigorated by fresh Swiss air after several years of digital interaction, attendees over the next five days enjoyed performances (both lecture-recitals and concerts), meetings of friends (old and new), and exciting exchanges of new scholarship. Conference papers varied widely, intertwining issues of social history, performance practice, and historiography. Prevalent topics included:

1. Book history and musical scribes.
2. Musicological advances in the digital humanities.
3. Travel and networks.
4. Architecture and urban space.
5. Music, rhetoric, and body politics.
6. Historiography of early music and contemporary performance practice.

While many papers engaged with book history, some specifically focused on music, knowledge-building, and literacy in the early modern world. Stephen Rose revealed new evidence of widespread musical literacy in late seventeenth-century rural England, as taught by local parish clerks in a wider effort to consolidate methods for learning psalms and Biblical texts. Andrew Frampton explored how library-building processes highlight hidden overlaps between collectors, copyists, and composers, using the music library of Johann Friedrich Agricola (1720-77) as a case study. Yo Tomita's new scribal identification for a J. S. Bach flute sonata presented a case study that de-centered the authority of the score, arguing that the copyist (argued to be Goldberg) exerted performer's agency through their interpretation of Bach's incomplete squiggle-slur.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, sessions concerning scribes and book history methodologies intersected closely with musicological developments in the digital humanities. Particularly exciting were advances in databases for musical scribes, such as the AteCop project (presented by Laurent Guillo and Pascal Dénecheau), a database of French music

copyists active up to the year 1730 with evidence of complex training or an active career outside France. The project successfully identified several unknown hands and highlighted new scribes needing identification. Anne Pićjus similarly revealed previously invisible agents by expanding upon musical aspects within the *Mercure Galant* database, emphasising how new developments in the database project illuminated women's central role in publishing, composing, engraving, and performing music in early modern France, albeit anonymised either as relations to male professional musicians or publishers, or constructed in idealised forms. Similarly, papers concerning musical travel and networks tracked more opaque or ephemeral musical agents, particularly in early modern wealthy households. Antonella d'Ovidio explored the *virtuose di musica* and epistolary evidence that demonstrated the processes for scouting and exchanging young, musically talented girls to act as quasi-professional musicians for seventeenth-century Italian aristocratic households, highlighting the value the scouts - always older men - placed on the girls' beauty and youth in comparison to their abilities. Maria Schildt offered a different way of assessing networks of exchange by examining codicological evidence within music manuscripts formerly belonging to the exceptionally wealthy Dutch-Swedish De Geer family, showing a wide variety of musical agents involved in acquiring, copying, and compiling the library.

A crucial strength of the Biennial Baroque conference is its draw for scholars interested in combining the study of historical musical texts (e.g., notated music, treatises, etc.) with histories of the senses, emotions, and urban spaces. One strand of this exploration was concerned with architectures of musicking, such as Noel O'Regan's whirlwind tour of three oratories in early seventeenth-century Rome. The tour in particular highlighted the overlaps of secular and sacred spaces, the gendered aspects of bodies in said spaces, and the implications of the sonic space within these oratories as loci for entrenching (or transgressing) social hierarchies. Margaret Murata's paper on tragicomedy and opera in early eighteenth-century Rome similarly highlighted how music and sound intertwined with constructions of scenery and scene types to build a liminal space in which performers could fluidly move between roles and don masks, either literally or metaphorically in the form of mixed vocalities or

subtle changes in language or tone. A round table held by Ferran Escrivà Llorca, Anna Tedesco, Andrea Bombi, Angela Fiore, Ilaria Grippaudo, and Tess Knighton complemented this theme by providing a reflective assessment of methodological and theoretical frameworks for study of early modern urban soundscapes. In comparing projects focused on Palermo, Valencia, and Barcelona, these six scholars offered crucial insights into how this subsection of musicological scholarship has evolved since its foundations in the 1990s, and where urban musicology as a field may profitably expand.

Papers also touched upon music, rhetoric, and the body. Cathal Twomey's careful analysis of *ombra* scenes in Marc-Antoine Charpentier's *Mors Saitilis et Jonathae* (c. 1681-82) as derived from Francesco Cavalli's *Giasona* (1649) highlighted Italian influences on broader social concerns over body politics, spiritual control, and gender in late seventeenth-century French opera. Body and racial politics came to the fore in Tomos Watkin's analysis of the 'zombie biopolitic' in *Le Turc généreux* (1735), in which Watkin problematised Rameau's sonic depiction of enslaved Black bodies in *Les Indes galantes*. Bettina Varwig's provocative exploration on early modern synaesthesia argued for conceiving music not as mere auditory matter, but a quasi-material substance. Broadening our connection of music beyond hearing to our other overlapping senses, she highlighted discourse on German Lutheran hymn singing as musical affect, penetrating the soul and hearts of listeners with divine sweetness.

The return to an in-person format facilitated a strong presence of performance demonstrations. Andrew Wong shed new light upon unwritten practices between French vocal traditions and violin playing: the *accent*, an non-notated gasp (if you see it, you'd make it too loud) gives escape tone figures another possible rhetorical shaping that emulates an inflected sob—a subtle embellishment demonstrated with great nuance and bow control. Aleksandra Brzówska explored Francesco Rognoni's *Selva de varii passaggi* (1620) and two Milanese nuns who received dedications in the anthology of virtuosic diminutions. This case study of female bodies performing the ephemeral art of diminution presented an exciting avenue in researching seventeenth-century publishing practices.

Musical instruments and their affordances highlighted the intertwine of organology and performance practice. Cyril Lacheze and Marion Weckerle's demonstration of a half-dozen string and wind instrument replicas showed new understandings gleaned from experimental archeology and applied history (as described by Lacheze and Weckerle: think climbing Mount Everest with equipment replicas from 1924 to learn about George Mallory's expedition). Their results offered strikingly different alternatives from the often stylish and tapered performances of other historical performance specialists. Inês d'Avena paradoxically called for musicians with modern recorders to *de-arrange* arrangements marketed for eighteenth-century amateurs. While octave displacements and avoiding difficult notes on historical recorders without double holes were the norm, performers using more modern models might reconsider and undo these modifications (a point well delivered by d'Avena's agile performance of her own arrangements). On a project still in its infancy, Donna Agrell, Giovanni Battista Graziadio, and Carlos Bertao reported on the revival and experimentations of reconstructed fagottini and tenoroons (nineteenth-century small sized bassoons), an important organological contribution to the burgeoning field of Romantic orchestral performance practice.

Performers also used the stage to demonstrate their prowess. Minh Đức Lê presented arias by the singer/composer Giovanni Buzzoleni (fl. 1682-1722), while Nicholas Kleinman explored Telemann's fugal writing for the viola da gamba. Sarah van Cornewal shared her processes of learning and memorising Telemann's flute fantasias by rewriting and improvising through the partimento tradition and informed by Mattheson's writing on key and affect (although which affect to embody when a transcription changes key remained an intriguing and perhaps irreconcilable riddle.) Thérèse de Goede's lecture on continuo treatises in Corelli's time presented at times surprisingly thick-textured realisations that elicited a lively question period.

The rich scholarship on early modern musical practices were accompanied by many explorations of modern early music cultures and practices. David Irving's investigation on the Dolmetsch family at the Haslemere festival in the 1920s and 30s raised questions on the socially-charged nature

of performing early music, specifically as an act of tradition building reliant on unsaid ideologies of 'lineage', conservation, and preservation. While Drew Edward Davies' exploration of Cathedral music in late seventeenth- and early eighteenth-century Mexico City was primarily concerned with uncovering and analysing historical sources, his paper nonetheless highlighted vital context that demonstrated the need for this research. This context demonstrated a consistent tendency in recordings and performances by contemporary European early music ensembles to implicitly (or in some cases, explicitly) portray the exoticised versions of 'New World' music composed by Europeans as true, and more importantly, the only surviving representations of early modern Central American music. These papers, among others, particularly insinuated how musicians and musicologists might undertake more introspective historiographies.

What next for the Biennial Baroque conference? There is much praise for this year's hosts, evinced above (and shortly, below). What can change or be reconsidered? The authors' reflections on the conference experience, based in part on conversations with fellow early career scholars, coalesced mainly on the following: the conference saw a distinctly less diverse body of attendees than previous iterations with few if any delegates from the global south, accompanied with a marked drop in attendance by early career scholars. The expensive nature of attending a conference in Switzerland (and particularly Geneva) was frequently discussed among the few early career scholars and graduate students attending, and the financial reality of little to no funding assistance for conference attendance (either by delegates' institutions, or by the conference hosts) reflects an additional layer of challenge. Future iterations of Biennial Baroque will have to contend with the financial implications of the geographic location to encourage attendance for the next crop of scholars, either in-person or online. Perhaps a steeper discount or even elimination of registration fees for a designated group of presenters might alleviate financial burdens. While hybrid conferencing presents other sets of challenges and is by no means a panacea, it has been shown to significantly broaden attendance. Assuming a similar lack of financial support in today's academic climate, a hybrid model would increase opportunities for networking across global regions, and at least

partially lower barriers that affect scholars from the global majority disproportionately. With adequate institutional investment in allocated technology teams, it can prove to be a remarkably smooth experience.

That said, as with last year's conference, the atmosphere of the conference was exceptionally amiable and supportive. Editors of *Early Music* fielded questions, solicited submissions, and offered attendees a sneak peak to its forthcoming issue celebrating 50 years of publication. A free day of organised activities provided a welcome break, including guided walks around the former Calvinist capital by local experts, and culminating with a sumptuous evening concert of J. S. Bach's cantatas performed by Gli Angeli Genève and students at the Haute École de Musique, with director Stephan MacLeod on double duty as bass soloist and director (Seung Kyung Lee's expert Baroque oboe

playing also shined.) The 20th Biennial International Conference provided a generative week of music-making and scholarly exchanges, and we look forward to following where these exciting avenues of research will take us when the next conference reconvenes in the United Kingdom, 2025.

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Reviews

Benjamin Cosyn, *Complete Keyboard Music*, ed. Orhan Memed, *Musica Britannica CVII* (London: Stainer and Bell, 2022). Hardback, 240pp., £125.00.

The last volume of English keyboard music from before c.1630 in *Musica Britannica* (MB) to be devoted to a single composer was my own Philips edition of 1999. There have been some which have mopped up anonymous pieces and those by composers whose output was insufficient for an entire volume (MB vols 96 and 102), but the lack of an edition of music by Benjamin Cosyn was an obvious lacuna: he was the one remaining significant composer of the so-called English virginalist school. As the acknowledged authority on Cosyn, Memed is an obvious choice of editor. But why have we waited for this edition for so long? It is not as though he were an unknown figure: his manuscripts were used as sources for the Bull volumes (MB vols 14 and 19). Memed points to Thurston Dart's suspicion of Cosyn's 'retouching' works by other composers. Indeed, there are other pieces, such as *The Queen's Command* (no. 14) which have their origins in works by other composers (in this case, Orlando Gibbons). We now have a greater sense of the active role played by scribes in transmitting this repertoire: Dart and his contemporaries saw it in terms of the nineteenth-century 'work concept', whereas today we are more aware of the nature of the manuscript sources of keyboard music and the inherent textual instability that comes about as player-scribes interact creatively with the music. Cosyn's reworkings of pieces (rather than works) by Byrd and Bull form a discrete section in the edition (nos 30–33b) and provide us with an insight into how a player appropriated music from previous generations, adapting it for his own use. It provides a salutary reminder that, perhaps to a lesser extent than here, most sources of late sixteenth- and early seventeenth-century English keyboard music reflect the performance practice of players other than the composer.

I suspect another reason why Cosyn has been overlooked is that none of his music features in any of the great anthologies such as Fitzwilliam Virginal Book. The reason we can be sure that it was Cosyn who adapted music by other composers is that it appears in a manuscript written by him, British Library, R. M. 23.i.4 (Co), which also contains the bulk of his own music. At some point, Cosyn obtained a manuscript associated with Bull, Paris, Bibliothèque Nationale de France, Réserve 1185 (Bu), to which he affixed a copy of *Parthenia* and added his own pieces in a newer style, as well as adding an index, dated 1652. His music does not seem to have been disseminated widely, and – unusually for this repertoire – we have only autograph sources, rather than manuscripts copied by scribes not necessarily close to the composer. All of Cosyn's pieces are unique to their source so there is no conflation of texts in Memed's edition. Indeed, they follow the transcriptions in volume two of the editor's *Seventeenth-Century Keyboard Music: Benjamin Cosyn*, but with the idiosyncratic separate flags for short note values replaced by beaming, modern conventions governing accidentals, and editorial emendation of the music where necessary.

Memed makes the not unreasonable assumption that Bu entered Cosyn's possession on Bull's move to the Continent in 1613. If so, it suggests a connection between the two that is borne out by Cosyn's likely origins in Shropshire when Bull was nearby in Hereford, and the flamboyant style of most of what is contained in Co. The inclusion of pieces by Bull alongside his own music in this manuscript, as well as his evident knowledge of Bull's music when compiling the index to Bu, suggest Bull was Cosyn's teacher. Memed divides Cosyn's music into several categories: works by the composer in Co; his versions of pieces by Byrd and Bull in Co; pieces in a more modern, mid-century style from Bu; voluntaries from Oxford, Christ Church Library Mus. 1113 that are probably by Cosyn; unattributed pieces possibly by him; and, finally, an appendix containing a setting of Dowland's *Lachrimae* which is ascribed to 'Mr

Cussen' in its source. Within each category, he sensibly preserves the order in which pieces occur.

Playing through the music, the impression is left of three distinct and very different musical personalities which raises questions of authorship. Could there be more than one composer at play? However, I remain sceptical about making such judgments based on stylistic evidence alone, and it is clear from Memed's introductory material that we are dealing with a composer who, as he points out, enjoyed a long career of fifty years, adapting his keyboard practice to changing fashion. Cosyn clearly carried on writing for keyboard until close to his death in 1653: some unattributed pieces in Bu make their way into the edition since they postdate the index. The voluntaries in the Christ Church manuscript are ascribed to 'B. C.', the same designation that Cosyn himself used when witting out his own music in Bu, which makes it reasonable to conclude that these pieces are by him as well. Memed considers the possible chronology of the corpus, suggesting that the voluntaries may have been student works, with the possible exception of no. 44 in the edition, which seems that much more mature. Ironically, it is probably this and no. 42 that will be known by keyboard players since they have been included in anthologies of organ music since the 1980s. Although I profess that they are two of my favourite pieces in the repertoire, they are not at all typical of Cosyn's music. Most of his pieces are dances. Memed's decision to preserve the sequence of music found in the sources means we can see that after three pavan and galliard pairs at the beginning of Co, Cosyn abandons the normal pairing of these dances in his music and, with the exception of a setting of a pair by Ives, includes only freestanding galliards from this point on.

The outgoing bravura of Cosyn's music places it firmly in the Bull tradition, and in virtuosity it surely surpasses the earlier composer. The technical difficulty lies not so much in the rapidity of the figuration (and note that the demisemiquavers here are original, unlike the doubled note values of the edition of Cosyn's contemporary, Tomkins – MB vol. 5), but in the need for lightening quick changes of hand position. There are numerous examples, such as the left hand of no. 17, or the right hand in no. 5, bar 69 or

in no. 6 from the end of bar 105 to the beginning of bar 106. Cosyn seems to have abandoned extreme technical display for a simpler, more refined style in the alman–coranto–saraband suites of Bu, much in the same way that Bull seems to have abandoned his virtuosic English style on encountering music by Sweelinck and others once he was on the Continent after 1613.

Like the majority of the so-called virginalists, Cosyn was an organist, holding positions at St Lawrence, Ludlow (1621), Dulwich College (1622–4) and Charterhouse (1626–43). Although Edward Alleyn's statutes for Dulwich date from after Cosyn had left, the description of duties is still relevant: he would have played the organ, sung in the choir, copied music for use in chapel and elsewhere within the college, directed the choir and taught the scholars to sing and play instruments, including organ and virginal. Puritan opposition to the use of the organ in church services led to the loss of job at Charterhouse, so it is possible that the suites reflect changes in his professional circumstances. Similarly, Memed points out that the music contained in Co dates from before it was indexed in 1620, which predates any known employment as organist; the style of the music marks it out as being for virginal, whereas music by Byrd and his pupils often works equally well on whatever instrument is to hand.

Cosyn writes full triads low in the keyboard compass on many an occasion – see, for example, the very first chord of no. 1. Of course, he may have wanted a thick, gruff effect; however, I wonder whether this writing implies something about the pitch of his instrument? There were four pitch levels found in England from c.1550 to c.1700, of which the highest (a1 at 473 Hz) was common for English virginals (see forthcoming article by Darryl Martin in *Scottish Music Review*, p. 9, n. 34).

I wonder whether there is any need nowadays to include modern time signatures, which bear little relation to sixteenth-century music theory? The mensuration signs given here between the staves are easy enough for any player to understand. I also wonder about Cosyn as a composer 'eager to explore virtuoso writing for the harpsichord', since

the only use of 'harpsichord' in printed sources published during Cosyn's lifetime occurs in Henry Hawkins's *Partheneia sacra* of 1633 in which there is reference to 'divisions on the Harpsicon or Virginals'. Of course, this is a question of terminology since, for example, the Theewes claviorgan of 1579 is harpsichord-shaped.

Anyone approaching this music as a performer should look at Memed's lucid and sensible guidance on playing the single- and double-stroke ornaments: undoubtedly their meaning evolved through time, but when playing through Cosyn's music, Memed's interpretation of the single stroke as a lower mordent (to use unashamedly modern terminology), and the double stroke as an upper one, worked consistently well in all circumstances.

Memed should be congratulated on this edition, which is of crucial importance to our understanding of early English keyboard music. The quality of the editing is first rate, as might be expected, and Memed's introduction provides a wealth of material. The appearance of an edition of Cosyn's music in MB helps to recalibrate our understanding of his place in music history: all that is needed now is for someone to record this technically challenging and exuberant music.

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Je languis nuit et jour

from *Le Bourgeois Gentilhomme*

Jean-Baptiste Moliere

Jean-Baptiste Lully

Je lan - guis nuit et jour, et mon mal est ex - trê - me De - puis qu'à vos ri -

gueurs vos beaux yeux m'ont sou - mis. mis. Si vous trai - tez ain - si, bel - le I - ris, qui_ vous

ai - me, Hé - las! hé - las! que pour - riez vous fai - re à vos en - ne - mis? Si

vous trai - tez ain - si, bel - le I - ris qui vous ai - me, Hé - las, hé -

las, que pour - riez vous fai - re à vos_ En - ne - mis. Si mis.

